

AMBIENT-6G

Towards standardized 6G connectivity for ambient-powered energy-neutral IoT devices

Deliverable D2.1

END architecture, technology trade-off, and characterization

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Authors:	Dragan Subotic (IMEC), Ritesh Singh (IMEC), Jarne Vanmulders (KUL), Lyssa Ramaut (KUL), Jona Cappelle (KUL), Lieven Destrycker (KUL), Gilles Callebaut (KUL), Mateen Ashraf (OUL), Onel López (OUL), Efstathios Katranaras (SEQ), Boxuan Xie (AAU), Kalle Koskinen (AAU), Riku Jäntti (AAU), Steven Sanders (QKS), Guus Leenders (QKS), Daniel Poehl (NXP), Ulrich Muehlmann (NXP), Bikramjit Singh (LMF), Benjamin Deutschmann (TUG), Lukas Dangelo (TUG), Miltiadis Filippou (WIN), Aimilia Bantouna (WIN).
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Abstract:

This deliverable contains a comprehensive analysis and selection process to determine the most appropriate technologies and materials for developing energy-neutral IoT devices. To achieve this goal, the device architectural component-based device capabilities are first divided into six isolated categories. Within these six capabilities, the energy storage and energy harvesting capabilities dictate the operational behavior of any underlying END and are therefore used to classify ENDs into multiple classes. Specifically, it is noted that an END can operate in one of the following modes: ultra-passive, duty-cycled barebone, duty-cycled persistent, or continuous. Based on this observation, this deliverable classifies ENDs into four classes: UP ENDs, DB ENDs, DP ENDs and CO ENDs. Moreover, the operational limits of individual capabilities, and typical applications are discussed for each device class.

Keywords:

AMBIENT-6G, Device Classification, Energy-Neutral Devices, Ambient-IoT, Technology Selection, Material Selection, End of Life, Life Cycle Assessment.

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Internal reviewers

Riku Jäntti (AAU)

Miltiadis Filippou (WIN)

Gilles Callebaut (KUL)

External reviewers

Kaveh Masoud (AAU)

Jeroen Famaey (IMEC)

Rubén Altuna Pérez (TEL)

Executive Summary

This document constitutes the issue of Deliverable D2.1: 'END architecture, technology trade-off, and characterization', within the framework of the project titled "AMBIENT-6G – Towards standardized 6G connectivity for ambiently-powered energy-neutral IoT devices" (Project Acronym: AMBIENT-6G; Grant Agreement No: 101192113).

The document first presents details of the architectural components of energy-neutral devices (ENDs) that can be used to categorize them. Next, it elaborates on the classification of ENDs using alpha-numeric coding. It also highlights the prototypes and case studies, along with use cases of the proposed device classes. Lastly, it provides an ecological assessment of the ENDs according to their used materials and manufacturing procedures.

In summary, the contents of this document are organized as follows:

- **Chapter 1** discusses the motivation, scope, objectives, and overall structure of the report.
- **Chapter 2** covers the most important END capabilities, such as energy storage, incoming energy, interfaces, processing, communication, and memory, for establishing classification codes of ENDs in this document. Moreover, it also illustrates the use of the proposed codes with examples of typical use cases.
- **Chapter 3** provides classifications, key features of the proposed END classifications along with their respective architectural and operational properties. Furthermore, a discussion related to existing prototypes and case studies is also included for each END type.
- **Chapter 4** is dedicated to the study of environmental impact of ENDs and strategies to improve the sustainability of the related Internet of Things (IoT) systems.
- **Chapter 5** concludes this document.

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Glossary

3GPP 3rd Generation Partnership Project.

5G Fifth-Generation.

6G sixth-generation.

ADC Analog-to-Digital Converter.

AI Artificial Intelligence.

AIoT Ambient-IoT.

AmBC Ambient BC.

AP access point.

API application program interface.

BC Backscatter Communication.

BD Backscatter Device.

BER bit error rate.

BFSK Binary Frequency Shift Keying.

BLE Bluetooth Low Energy.

BS Base Station.

BTS Base Transceiver Station.

CMOS Complementary Metal Oxide Semiconductor.

CN Core Network.

CO Continuous-Operation.

COTS Commercial off-the-shelf.

CPU Central-Processing Unit.

CSI Channel State Information.

DAC Digital-to-Analog Converter.

DB Duty-Cycled Barebone.

DC Direct Current.

DLI Direct Link Interference.

DP Duty-Cycled Persistent.

DRAM Dynamic RAM.

EDLC Electrostatic Double-Layer Capacitors.

EEPROM Electrically EPROM.

EH Energy Harvesting.

EM electromagnetic.

eMBB Enhanced Mobile Broadband.

END energy-neutral device.

EoL End of Life.

EPROM Erasable Programmable ROM.

eRedCap enhanced RedCap.

ESL Electronic Shelf Label.

FET Field-Effect Transistor.

FRAM Ferroelectric RAM.

FS Faradaic supercapacitor.

GNSS Global Navigation Satellite System.

GPIO General-Purpose Input/Output.

GPS Global Positioning System.

GWP Global Warming Potential.

I2C Inter-Integrated Circuit.

IC Integrated Circuit.

IoT Internet of Things.

ISM Industrial, Scientific and Medical.

KPI Key Performance Indicator.

KVI Key Value Indicator.

LCA Life Cycle Assessment.

LDO Low-Dropout Voltage Regulator.

LDPC low-density parity-check.

LED Light Emitting Diode.

LFP Lithium Iron Phosphate.

LIC Lithium-Ion Capacitor.

LoRaWAN Long-Range Wide-Area Network.

LTE Long Term Evolution.

LTE-M Long-Term Evolution Machine Type Communication.

LTO Lithium Titanate.

LWA Leaky-Wave Antenna.

M2M Machine-to-Machine.

MCU Microcontroller Unit.

MEMS micro-electromechanical systems.

MIMO Multiple-Input Multiple-Output.

MIPS Million Instructions Per Second.

ML Machine Learning.

MLCC Multi-Layer Ceramic Capacitor.

mMTC massive Machine-Typed Communication.

MRAM Magnetoresistive RAM.

NB-IoT Narrowband IoT.

NCA Nickel Cobalt Aluminum.

NFC Near-Field Communication.

NIC Na-ion Capacitor.

NiCd Nikkel Cadmium.

NiMH Nikkel Metal Hydride.

NMC Nickel Manganese Cobalt.

NR New Radio.

NVM Non-Volatile Memory.

OAuth Open Authorization.

OFDM Orthogonal Frequency-Division Multiplexing.

OTP One-Time-Programmable.

PCB Printed Circuit Board.

PCE Power Conversion Efficiency.

PEET Polyethylene Terephthalate.

PER packet error rate.

PMU Power Management Unit.

PoC Proof-of-Concept.

PUF Physical Unclonable Function.

PV Photovoltaic.

PWM Pulse Width Modulation.

QoS Quality-of-Service.

RAM Random-Access Memory.

RAN Radio Access Network.

RCS Radar Cross Section.

RF Radio Frequency.

RFID RF Identification.

RIS Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface.

ROM Read-Only Memory.

RRC Radio Resource Control.

RX Receiver.

SDG sustainable development goal.

SDR Software-Defined Radio.

SIR Signal-to-Interference Ratio.

SLAM simultaneous localization and mapping.

SMA Sub-Miniature Version A.

SMT Surface Mount Technology.

SPI Serial Peripheral Interface.

SRAM Static RAM.

SRM State-Retention Memory.

TDD Time Division Duplexing.

TX Transmitter.

UART Universal Asynchronous Receiver/Transmitter.

UAV Unmanned Aerial Vehicle.

UE User Equipment.

UHF Ultra-High Frequency.

UID unique ID.

UP Ultra-Passive.

URLLC Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communications.

UWB Ultra Wideband.

VLC Visible Light Communication.

WPT Wireless Power Transfer.

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Emerging Internet of Things (IoT) technologies and applications are expected to transform future networks into systems comprising a massive number of low-power heterogeneous devices. A critical challenge here is to ensure dependable and energy-efficient connectivity, while simultaneously addressing broader sustainability objectives. In this context, sustainable connectivity denotes a paradigm in wireless communications where devices operate autonomously, are environmentally friendly, and can still realize their intended societal and economic impact. Central to this vision are energy-neutral devices (ENDs), which AMBIENT-6G defines as IoT devices that exploit ambient Energy Harvesting (EH) or Radio Frequency (RF)-Wireless Power Transfer (WPT) to recharge their energy storage and subsequently power their operation. This avoids frequent battery replacement or wired power sources and enables decades-long energy autonomy.

Figure 1.1: Classification of low-power IoT devices, while illustrating the definition of energy neutrality.

Figure 1.2: General architecture of active and passive ENDs. The application related hardware can include memory, and interfaces.

ENDs may comprise active and passive (i.e., backscattered-based) radios in either battery-powered or battery-free implementations as illustrated in Figure 1.1 and Figure 1.2. Note that the END architecture may comprise several components to support a variety of functions in addition to radios and energy storage, such as processors, peripherals, and/or memory. This means the existing device classifications, for example, Ambient-IoT (AIoT) device classification from 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) [1], which are based merely on their energy storage capacity and their ability to generate RF signals for transmissions, are unable to cover the full spectrum of ENDs. A summary of the current device classifications with respect to the described architectural components is provided in Table 1.1. In fact, the END classification and characterization, covering a wider range of ENDs, proposed through this deliverable, will contribute to the development of device capability-adaptable network architectures and protocol designs for their energy-efficient operations.

1.2 Scope and objectives

Within the context of AMBIENT-6G, this deliverable provides the necessary meeting point between WP2, WP4, and WP5 by providing characterization of the ENDs as input to T4.1 and T5.1, while taking Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and Key Value Indicators (KVIs) from T5.1. Specifically, device classification proposed through this deliverable can be used to identify which device classes can be used in each use case from D5.1. Moreover, this deliverable establishes a means for interaction between WP2 and WP3, where the capabilities of the ENDs developed in WP2 set constraints for the network architecture and protocols developed in T3.1, T3.2, and T3.3.

To incorporate the energy neutrality aspect of IoT devices, it is necessary to depart from conventional classification criteria, such as latency, scale, and capacity, used in 5G systems. To this end, the conceived criteria include energy storage (essential for autonomous operation), incoming (harvested) energy (type and availability), peripherals (sensing/control abilities), processing (local intelligence), communication (data exchange), and memory capabilities (state retention). The selection of these criteria is motivated by the generic END architecture (see Figure 1.2), which can be divided into the five aforementioned major operational components.

Table 1.1: Summary of existing device classifications.

Classification name	Description	(Number of classes) Classes names and applicability to low-power IoT networks
5G device classification [2]	service types based classification such as eMBB, mMTC and URLLC. This classification is based on communication QoS aspects such as data rate, reliability, ubiquitousness etc. The devices are not classified according to their architectural components.	(3) {eMBB 5G devices, fixed wireless access 5G devices, industrial 5G devices}. All classes except for eMBB 5G devices can be used for low-power IoT applications.
6G device classification [3]	enhancement of 5G device classifications and new classes based on energy, reliability, and latency needs. The classification is not based on the architectural components of the device.	(4) {reliable high data rate with bounded latency devices, highly reliable low latency device class, enhancements of mMTC device class, and END}. Except for reliable high data rate with bounded latency devices, the remaining classes can be used in low-power IoT applications.
AIoT device classification by 3GPP [4]	classification of low-power/energy devices based on their energy storage capacity and their ability to generate RF signals for transmissions. Although this classification considers architectural components of the devices, it is limited to energy and communication aspects only.	(3) {Device A, Device B, Device C}. All device classes can be used in IoT applications.
LoRaWAN device classification [5]	devices are categorized on the basis of transmit power, synchronous/asynchronous communication, and deterministic/lowest latency capabilities.	(3) {Class A, Class B, Class C}. All device classes can be used in IoT applications.

1.3 Structure of the document

This deliverable is divided into five chapters. The characterization criteria and the proposed classification coding scheme are provided in Chapter 2. Individual END classes are introduced and discussed in Chapter 3. The ecological assessment regarding each individual END class is conducted in Chapter 4. Finally, this deliverable is concluded in Chapter 5.

Chapter 2

Device capability categories

This section describes the capabilities of typical wireless ENDs. The goal is to categorize device capabilities, and refine each category into subclasses of higher granularity. A predefined device capability encoding scheme is used to assign a class and a corresponding range of subclasses to a typical END. This allows comparison of devices with similar implementations.

Characterizing and distinguishing ENDs based on their fundamental architectural building blocks offers several advantages. Devices sharing similar codes can be systematically categorized (as in the classes specified in Chapter 3) and ranked, facilitating comparative analysis. Moreover, it helps identify devices with higher energy demands and greater implementation complexity. Furthermore, the correlation between environmental impact and the selected codes will be analyzed in Chapter 4 and further elaborated in subsequent deliverables of this work package. This analysis is justified by the intrinsic link between performance categories and hardware characteristics, as the sustainability impact of a device is predominantly dictated by its hardware composition and design. The END classification can also help an IoT service provider in decisions related to the deployment of a certain volume of ENDs of one category compared to another category, depending on the results of a cost/benefit analysis.

2.1 Subcategories and their description

The capabilities of an END are illustrated in Figure 2.1, which is a more concise version of that presented in [6]. There is a strong connection to the architecture presented in Figure 1.2. Although, this chapter begins with a more general architecture, without revealing specific design choices, and clarifies that ENDs can be implemented in various ways, using different sources of incoming energy. The key hardware components required to build a END consist of the following elements. An **energy storage** device is used for storing (harvested) energy. An energy converter distributes the **incoming energy** directly to the consumers or stores it in the energy storage device. A **processing** unit manages sensor data, monitors energy consumption, communicates with peripheral components, etc. The **peripherals** serve as the interface with external components, such as sensors, actuators, localization modules, etc. The **communication** interface, which in an END can be either an active radio, or a passive backscatter-based radio. Finally, **memory** is also considered a key component in this architecture. Note that although we elaborate on several hardware components, not all of them are present in all ENDs, as we will see in Chapter 3.

Figure 2.1: Generalized architecture of the capabilities of a END, adapted from [6]. While incoming energy, peripherals, and (RF) communication are illustrated as distinct components interfacing with the physical world, these functions can often be combined in practice: for example, a solar panel may also serve as a light sensor, or an RF antenna may be used both for communication and energy harvesting.

The proposed performance categories adhere to a structured classification system, in which each hardware component is assigned a letter (ranging from *A* to *F*) representing a broad hardware category. To further refine the characterization of a component, numerical subcategories are appended to the corresponding letter. This alphanumeric classification enables a concise yet comprehensive representation of specific hardware configurations.

An overview of the specific configurations within each category, and how they can be linked to a device, is provided in Table 2.1. The following sections elaborate on the different categories and subcategories, explaining how each classification code corresponds to a specific hardware component.

Table 2.1: Overview table on the proposed classification methods for wireless ENDS.

General classification	Sub-classification	Sub-sub-classification	Sub-sub-sub-classification
A: Energy storage	0: No storage 1: Electrostatic 2: Hybrid 3: Electrochemical	#0: <10 mJ #1: 10-100 mJ #2: 100 m-1 J #3: 1-10 J #4: 10-100 J #5: 100 J-1 kJ #6: 1-10 kJ #7: 10-100 kJ #8: >100kJ	
B: Incoming energy	0: None 1: Scavenging / harvesting 2: Uncoupled WPT 3: Coupled WPT	#0: None #1: Electromagnetic (photovoltaic) #2: Electromagnetic (RF) #3: Magnetic field (inductive) #4: Electric field (capacitive) #5: Mechanical wave (acoustic) #6: Heat #7: Vibration #8: Flow	
C: Interfaces	0: None 1: Digital 2: Analog 3: RF	#0: None #1: GPIO #2: Bus #3: ADC #4: DAC #5: Comparator #6: Sensing #7: Positioning #8: Localization	
D: Processing	0: Without CPU 1: <1 MIPS 2: 1-10 MIPS 3: 10-100 MIPS 4: 100-1000 MIPS 5: >1000 MIPS	#0: No signal processing #1: Rule based #2: Signal processing/filtering #3: Statistical/predictive methods #4: Data compression #5: ML/AI	##0: No security ##1: Physical layer security ##2: Hardware layer security ##3: Firmware layer security ##4: Network layer security ##5: App layer security
E: Communication	0: None 1: Passive 2: Semi-passive 3: Active	#0: None #1: RF #2: Optical #3: Mechanical waves (e.g., acoustic) #4: Magnetic induction	##0: <1 kbps ##1: 1-10 kbps ##2: 10-100 kbps ##3: 100 k-1 Mbps ##4: >1 Mbps
F: Memory	0: None 1: RAM 2: SRM 3: ROM	#0: <1 kB #1: 1-64 kB #2: 64-512 kB #3: 512 kB-8 MB #4: >8 MB	

2.1.1 Energy storage

The energy storage of an END can generally be categorized into three types: **electrostatic**, **hybrid**, and **electrochemical** technologies. The hybrid storage technologies are a combination of electrostatic and electrochemical principles. In this categorization, the hybrid technology has been defined before the electrochemical category, as it is sorted according to increasing energy density and decreasing power density [7]. For completeness, storage-less devices are also included.

	A	#	#
Storage technologies			Capacity levels
0 No storage			0 <10 mJ
1 Electrostatic			1 10-100 mJ
2 Hybrid			2 100 m-1 J
3 Electrochemical			3 1-10 J
			4 10-100 J
			5 100 J-1 kJ
			6 1-10 kJ
			7 10-100 kJ
			8 >100 kJ

Figure 2.2: Categorization of energy storage technologies and their corresponding capacity levels.

A further refinement is presented by defining multiple ranges of capacity levels as subcategories, as shown in Figure 2.2. It is important to note that other features, such as cycle life, energy density, power density, shelf life, etc., are not included in this classification. This decision was made to limit complexity, and these features are also partly related to the chosen technology. Although, it should be noted that features within these storage technologies can still vary within a certain range. For instance, energy and power density in electrochemical batteries can vary significantly when comparing different chemistries. Further clarifications can be found in Sections 2.1.1.1 to 2.1.1.3.

2.1.1.1 Electrostatic energy storage devices

In an END, it is expected that the energy storage capacity is either nonexistent (e.g., in passive ENDS) or very limited. For example, RF Identification (RFID) tags do not have any energy storage capabilities and are, therefore, categorized under the A00 code. When the power densities of the harvesters from Section 2.1.2 are limited, short-term buffering can be provided.

Before discussing electrostatic storage technologies, it is clarified that energy capacity is expressed in joules to ensure a consistent and general comparison. Electrostatic energy storage devices are typically expressed in Farad. The relation between the stored energy [J] and the capacity [F] is represented in Equation (2.1).

$$E = \frac{1}{2}C (V_{charge}^2 - V_{min}^2) \quad (2.1)$$

- E is the usable energy capacity.
- C the capacitance of an electrostatic energy storage devices.
- V_{charge} is the charging voltage and is partially determined by the incoming energy and the energy conversion characteristics. This is further elaborated in Section 2.1.2.
- V_{min} is the minimum voltage at which the end device can operate, either directly or via a DC/DC converter capable of boosting it to the required voltage level.

Aluminum or polymer capacitors with capacitances ranging from tens of μF to several mF can be selected and are categorized under A10 to A12. Electrostatic Double-Layer Capacitors (EDLCs), also known as supercapacitors, fall under this Electrostatic category as well. Their

typical capacitance ranges from a few mF up to hundreds of F, covering codes A12 to A16. Due to this overlap in A12, in some applications, a choice can be made between aluminum, polymer, and EDLC storage technologies. The power density of aluminum and polymer capacitors is generally much higher than that of EDLCs. However, this comes at the cost of lower energy density. In other words, for the A12 category, integrating an aluminum or polymer capacitor requires more physical space, with the advantage that the stored energy can be delivered within a shorter time span.

Other capacitors, such as ceramic capacitors, film capacitors, and Multi-Layer Ceramic Capacitors (MLCCs), are less suitable for short-term energy storage ranging from several seconds to hours due to their relatively higher self-discharge rate and low energy densities.

Electrostatic Storage technologies ⇒ Applicable capacity levels								
0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8

2.1.1.2 Hybrid energy storage devices

In some devices, hybrid capacitors can be the preferred storage solution. Hybrid supercapacitors or Lithium-Ion Capacitors (LICs) consist of a battery-type anode and a capacitive-type cathode. The charge storage occurs through a combination of electrostatic and electrochemical processes, making them asymmetric electrodes.

The operating voltage is typically more attractive, ranging between 2.2 V and 3.8 V. The capacitance of such storage devices is similar to that of supercapacitors, with the significant difference being that the energy density can be up to 10 times higher. When designing ENDS, it's important to note that these hybrid capacitors should not be discharged down to 0 V, whereas EDLCs and pseudocapacitors can be fully discharged without causing damage [8].

Recent studies also investigate the feasibility of Na-ion Capacitors (NICs). Since lithium is much scarcer compared to sodium, interest in this new storage technology is increasing, as indicated in [9], [10].

Hybrid Storage technologies ⇒ Applicable capacity levels								
0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8

2.1.1.3 Electrochemical energy storage devices

Electrochemical storage devices convert and store energy through chemical reactions. Rechargeable and non-rechargeable batteries are commonly classified as storage devices, utilizing internal redox reactions during charging and discharging. The capacity is typically expressed in (m)Ah.

Additionally, Faradaic supercapacitors (FSs) or pseudocapacitors also belong to this category. The underlying principles are discussed in more detail in [11, Chapter 13]. When a voltage is applied to an FS, rapid and reversible Faradaic reactions (redox processes) occur at the electrode surfaces, facilitating charge transfer across the double layer. This mechanism is analogous to the charge and discharge cycles in batteries, leading to the flow of Faradaic current through the supercapacitor cell. Ongoing research clearly shows the distinction between EDLC, pseudocapacitor and batteries [12]. The capacity of a pseudocapacitor is expressed in F.

Figure 2.3: Possible types of incoming energy categories and various energy transfer mechanisms for ENDs.

Batteries are available in a wide range, from a few tens of mA h [13] to several A h, with nominal cell voltages ranging from 1.2V for nickel-based batteries [14] to 3.7V for certain lithium cells. For short term storage Lithium Titanate (LTO) cell [15] or even a Rechargeable multilayer ceramic chip from TDK with no liquid electrolyte can be considered for ENDs [16]. Besides these battery solutions, pseudocapacitors typically have lower capacitance values, in the order of tens to hundreds of F. It is concluded that these two electrochemical storage solutions primarily cover the subcategories ranging from A34 to A38. EDLCs and hybrid capacitors explained in Sections 2.1.1.1 and 2.1.1.2 are currently more commercially available technologies compared to pseudocapacitors. This could be explained by the degradation of electrode materials in these pseudocapacitors, which leads to a significant barrier to their widespread acceptance in the supercapacitor market [17].

Electrochemical Storage technologies ⇒ Applicable capacity levels								
0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8

2.1.2 Incoming energy

Either complete dependence of any operation on the reflected energy or its powering through harvested energy is essential for energy neutrality. As shown in Figure 2.3, incoming energy for EH can be categorized according to three modes of operation: **scavenging/harvesting**, **uncoupled WPT**, and **coupled WPT**. The *mode* of incoming energy signifies the cause of primary energy availability in the ambient environment. Further classification is achieved according to the available energy transfer mechanisms, which also suggests the type of hardware needed at the END side to harvest incoming energy. It is worth mentioning that a particular mode of operation may be supported by multiple energy transfer mechanisms. Likewise, a particular energy transfer mechanism can enable multiple modes of operations. A short summary of the required energy harvesters and the physical phenomenon for each of the energy transfer mechanism is provided in Table 2.2.

According to Figure 2.3, ENDs with B1 code harvest energy from ambient sources while ENDs with B2/B3 code rely on external power sources or transmitters. For the case when an END accomplishes its operation passively (e.g., by reflecting the incoming energy, see "Iridescent"

Table 2.2: Energy harvesters and corresponding physical phenomena for each transfer mechanism [18].

Energy transfer mechanism	Energy harvester	Underlying physical phenomenon
None	not applicable	not applicable
Electromagnetic (Photovoltaic)	Photovoltaic cells	Photovoltaic effect
Electromagnetic (RF)	Rectenna	Faraday's law of electromagnetic induction and rectification
Magnetic field	coupled coils	Faraday's law of electromagnetic induction
Electric field	capacitive plates	Capacitance coupling
Mechanical wave (acoustic)	Piezoelectric transducer	Piezoelectric effect
Heat	Thermoelectric generator	Thermoelectric or Seebeck effect
Vibration	Piezo/Triboelectric, Electrostatic and Vibration EM energy harvester	Piezoelectric or Triboelectric effect
Flow	Piezo/Triboelectric, Electrostatic and Vibration EM energy harvester	Piezoelectric or Triboelectric effect

reflective tags to enable radar-based orientation estimation" in Section 3.1.2 on page 27 for details), the device incoming energy is encoded as B00. However, when EH is performed within the END, the corresponding operation modes and respective energy transfer mechanisms are discussed in more detail next, together with their possible application scenarios.

2.1.2.1 Energy scavenging/harvesting

The devices within this category scavenge energy from the environment, available in the form of electromagnetic field, heat, vibration, and flow. The incoming energy in this category is uncontrollable/unpredictable, hence, it is harvested in an opportunistic manner only. However, EH performance can be significantly improved by adjusting factors like location, orientation, and transducer size.

There are six different energy transfer mechanisms (i.e., possible with device codes B1X, where $X \in \{1, 2, 6, 7, 8, 9\}$) for this form of incoming energy. The choice of a particular energy transfer mechanism depends on the energy, charging times, and form factors/complexity needs [18], [19]. For example, if scavenging is enabled through *electromagnetic* energy transfer mechanism B11, a few hundreds of mW/cm^2 of harvesting power is typically available in outdoor conditions during daytime, hence corresponding ENDS may suit applications where light is abundantly available. On the other hand, ENDS with code B17, where the *vibration* is the energy transfer mechanism with power densities ranging from a few $\mu W/cm^2$ to a few mW/cm^2 , are more suitable for wearable technology. The ENDS with code B16 rely on temperature gradients for EH. The power density is directly proportional to the temperature gradient, where a few Kelvins of temperature gradient can produce a power density in the range of a few hundred $\mu W/cm^2$. Finally, ENDS with codes B18 are dependent on wind/water flow-based EH. Such a dependence makes these devices suitable for automotive technologies such as terrestrial/non-terrestrial/underwater vehicles.

Scavenging / harvesting ⇒ Applicable energy transfer mechanisms								
0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8

2.1.2.2 Uncoupled WPT

This mode of operation provides some degree of control over the amount of harvested energy. In contrast to the first mode (scavenging/harvesting), where primary energy is available due to the result of some natural/non-dedicated phenomenon, herein, it is generated synthetically. Hence, the available power density at the energy harvester can be somewhat controlled.

A prominent example of possible energy transfer mechanisms in this mode is RF-based WPT with the corresponding END code B22. The RF energy transfer is achieved by transmitting RF energy signals from dedicated power beacon(s). The RF signals travel through the intervening medium to reach the intended END. The losses incurred due to Direct Current (DC)-RF conversion at the transmitter side, propagation of RF waves over the intervening medium, and RF-DC conversion at the energy harvester side, causing the end-to-end EH efficiency (or DC-DC efficiency) to be significantly small. However, this mode of operation is particularly useful for those ENDS that are located indoors or where ambient energy is not available.

Uncoupled WPT ⇒ Applicable energy transfer mechanisms								
0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8

2.1.2.3 Coupled WPT

This type of operation can be enabled by either magnetic field (i.e., B23), electric field (i.e., B24), or acoustic wave (i.e., B25) energy transfer mechanisms. This form of WPT is prone to misalignment between the coupling coils. In *electric field coupling*, two pairs of transmit and receive plates induce a capacitive coupling, where one pair forwards the displacement current while the other provides the return path to close the circuit. Although capacitive coupling is more robust to plate misalignment, controlling fringing electric fields is a critical issue. Meanwhile, acoustic wave energy transfer mechanism relies on the pressure waves generated by acoustic energy. These pressure waves cause vibrations in the piezoelectric transducers, thus, resulting in voltage generation at the receiver due to the piezoelectric effect. In contrast to electromagnetic WPT, such as inductive or capacitive coupling, the transmitters and receivers used in acoustic wave coupling have a small form factor. However, due to the possibility of hearing impairments and body heating in humans and animals, the intensity of acoustic waves must be controlled appropriately.

A major limitation of coupled WPT as compared to uncoupled WPT is that the power transfer distance for coupled WPT is smaller than that of uncoupled WPT.

Coupled WPT ⇒ Applicable energy transfer mechanisms								
0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8

2.1.3 Interfaces

To systematically classify the peripheral interfaces of ENDS, a structured categorization scheme is used, as highlighted in Figure 2.4. Three main interface categories are used to differentiate

Figure 2.4: Categorization of the device peripherals with all sub-categories for different interface types.

possible interfaces: **digital**, **analog**, and **RF**. The sub-categories further follow the classification of typical interfaces, often known from Microcontroller Units (MCUs) and technical datasheets.

Possible combinations of interface category and interface type is highlighted by the first digit of the interface type number.

2.1.3.1 No interface

Devices that have no defined peripheral interface are classified as **C00**. For instance, inventory RFID labels fall into this *no-interface* category since they do not implement external connections to other devices.

2.1.3.2 Digital interfaces

Digital interfaces are further categorized into two main subcategories: **General-Purpose Input/Output (GPIO)** and **bus** interfaces. GPIO interfaces consist of single or multiple digital pins of the END (not specifically designated for any particular function). The bus sub-category summarizes all potential bus interfaces, including protocols such as Inter-Integrated Circuit (I2C), Serial Peripheral Interface (SPI), or Universal Asynchronous Receiver/Transmitter (UART), among many others.

Digital Interfaces ⇒ Possible Interface Type								
0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8

2.1.3.3 Analog interfaces

Analog interfaces can be divided into three subcategories: **Analog-to-Digital Converter (ADC)**, **Digital-to-Analog Converter (DAC)**, and **comparator** interfaces. When an analog interface serves as a peripheral of the END, some of its pins operate within the analog domain, which can range from ground level up to the supply voltage of the device. If the supply voltage differs from the analog voltage domain, this must be specifically stated.

Analog Interfaces ⇒ Possible Interface Type								
0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8

a low-power network. Meanwhile, medium-MIPS devices, such as Arm Cortex M4 and M7, operate around 100 MIPS to 1000 MIPS and support real-time signal processing, secure execution environments, and multitasking applications, such as local sensor fusion in smart home systems. Finally, high-MIPS devices, including advanced edge computing platforms such as the NVIDIA Jetson series, can exceed 100 000 MIPS, allowing computationally intensive tasks such as on-device model training, real-time video analysis, and simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM) applications.

2.1.4.2 Workload types

The extent and nature of the data processing performed on the device is characterized by the second subclassification. Devices at level 0 perform no local processing and often act as passive data transmitters, such as IoT devices that gather simple sensor data and forward it. Subsequently, level 1 encompasses rule-based processing, where devices execute predefined logical operations, such as a smart thermostat that activates a heating system when a threshold temperature is met. Level 2 devices implement fundamental signal processing techniques, such as noise filtering in heart rate monitors to increase measurement accuracy. Level 3 includes statistical and predictive analytics, as observed in smart meters that forecast electricity consumption trends based on historical data. Level 4 devices employ data compression techniques to optimize storage or communication bandwidth usage. Finally, at level 5, devices integrate Machine Learning (ML) or Artificial Intelligence (AI), exemplified by camera-enabled IoT devices that perform on-device object or person recognition.

Rule based workload ⇒ Computational capacity					
0	1	2	3	4	5

Signal processing/filtering workload ⇒ Computational capacity					
0	1	2	3	4	5

Statistical / predictive workload ⇒ Computational capacity					
0	1	2	3	4	5

Data compression workload ⇒ Computational capacity					
0	1	2	3	4	5

ML/AI workload ⇒ Computational capacity					
0	1	2	3	4	5

2.1.4.3 Security capabilities

The third subclassification evaluates the security architecture of a device using a layer-based approach. This classification determines where security is embedded: no security, physical layer, hardware layer, firmware layer, network layer, or application layer. Note that devices may implement multiple security layers simultaneously, depending on their criticality and threat model.

Devices that lack any security measures are classified as level 0. Level 1 represents the lowest level of security implemented and addresses physical threats, including physical access control,

2.1.5.2 Communication medium

Depending on application-specific requirements, different mediums can be utilized:

- **RF:** This is the dominant medium in IoT communication, employing either backscatter modulation or active RF transceivers. RF allows a flexible communication range from a few meters (passive tags) up to hundreds of meters or even kilometers (active transmission) [22]. The device architecture can vary considerably depending on the required capabilities. A passive device usually consists of an antenna, impedance modulator, RF energy harvester, and minimal digital logic circuits. Backscatter modulation is performed by changing the antenna load impedance, reflecting incident RF signals with modulated information. Devices may integrate energy storage elements such as supercapacitors or small rechargeable batteries, allowing intermittent amplification of the reflected RF signal. Active devices feature dedicated RF transceiver components (such as oscillators, mixers, and amplifiers), enabling independent generation of RF signals. In addition, these architectures often incorporate Power Management Units (PMUs) and MCUs to efficiently optimize power usage and processing capabilities. For backscatter-based architectures AIoT, standardization efforts promote simple, robust, and scalable architectures, focusing on minimizing complexity and power consumption [1].
- **Optical (e.g., Visible Light Communication (VLC)):** Offers secure and interference-resistant data transmission but limited range and line of sight restrictions [23]. VLC is generally used where RF interference is a significant concern or the RF spectrum is crowded. EH via, e.g., solar cells can facilitate passive and semi-passive VLC solutions.
- **Mechanical waves (e.g., acoustic):** Suitable for challenging environments such as underwater IoT or industrial applications, where RF or optical means face severe attenuation [23]. Acoustic wave-based IoT generally operates at low data rates as acoustic signals encounter physical limitations (slower propagation, narrower bandwidth, more interference, and energy loss over distance) imposed by the medium (air, water, solid structures). While passive and semi-passive acoustic communication is feasible, practical deployments are typically rare due to energy harvesting challenges (acoustic signals have inherently low energy densities), limited efficiency (piezoelectric-based energy harvesters produce limited power unless there is intense and continuous mechanical vibration), and physical constraints (difficult for semi-passive to amplify or regenerate acoustic signals).
- **Magnetic induction:** Primarily used for very short-range, reliable, and secure communication, and typically used in healthcare, personal wearables, and implantable devices due to safety constraints and signal propagation benefits through biological tissues and barriers.

Passive ⇒ Applicable communication medium				
0	1	2	3	4

Semi-passive ⇒ Applicable communication medium				
0	1	2	3	4

Active ⇒ Applicable communication medium				
0	1	2	3	4

2.1.5.3 Data rate classification

Achievable data rate and respective requirements (such as energy consumption) for IoT devices can vary significantly based on the complexity of tasks/applications and the communication protocols used. 3GPP standardization efforts, for example, define AIoT use cases spanning various ranges [24].

- <1 kbps: Common in passive RF backscatter systems (e.g., RFID), used extensively for simple identification, asset tracking, and basic telemetry applications. 3GPP Rel.19 AIoT standards emphasize on ultra-low-power solutions (with target peak power consumption, i.e., during transmission, of less than 1 uW) fitting this data-rate category [25].
- 1-10 kbps: More related to semi-passive solutions (with expected peak power consumption between 1 uW and 1 mW), supporting environmental monitoring, basic sensor networks, and smart home scenarios.
- 10-100 kbps: Common in active IoT systems (such as expected active AIoT with peak power consumption expected around 1-10 mW, or legacy cellular Narrowband IoT (NB-IoT) and Long-Term Evolution Machine Type Communication (LTE-M) with peak power consumption in the range of 100 mW, towards the higher end of the rate range) for smart metering and industrial monitoring.
- 100 kbps - 1 Mbps: Supports relatively advanced IoT applications, including real-time data collection from multiple sensors, audio transmission, and enhanced industrial monitoring and control systems.
- >1 Mbps: Pertinent for IoT applications involving rich multimedia data, real-time video feeds, or complex industrial automation requiring rapid feedback. Such requirements typically exceed AIoT/END specifications due to power consumption constraints but are achievable with conventional cellular IoT (e.g., LTE-M, Long Term Evolution (LTE) Cat1(bis), New Radio (NR) enhanced RedCap (eRedCap) [26]).

Passive ⇒ Applicable data rates				
0	1	2	3	4

Semi-passive ⇒ Applicable data rates				
0	1	2	3	4

Active ⇒ Applicable data rates				
0	1	2	3	4

Acoustic/Magnetic ⇒ Applicable data rates				
0	1	2	3	4

RF/Optical ⇒ Applicable data rates				
0	1	2	3	4

It is noted that achievable data rate is especially important for scenarios with abundant data generation at the END side where devices have backlogged or streaming data of high volume. In case of scarce and/or bursty traffic, where devices have to generate and sample data less

frequently or with inconsistent periodicity, communication reliability (e.g., bit error rate (BER) or packet error rate (PER)) is a more crucial capability metric, which can be achieved with the implementation of coding techniques at the END side (e.g., polar or low-density parity-check (LDPC) coding). Such a coding scheme capability may also require different memory and data storage capabilities.

2.1.5.4 Communication architecture

The communication architecture supporting ENDS may still consist of two entities: Core Network (CN) and Radio Access Network (RAN). The CN facilitates the management of subscriber information, data and internet connectivity, and coordination with the RAN. The RAN provides connectivity between the END and the CN. Over the course of evolution, these entities, or certain aspects of them, may converge or leverage virtualization. Specifically for the RAN, expansion into various segments is expected, be it centralized, open, or virtualized¹. With ultra-low-power IoT devices receiving increased attention, the RAN, and possibly the CN, may need to be adapted or be equipped with new features and functions to handle specific communication challenges/requirements, for instance, ensuring a suitable RF medium for passive ENDS, or requiring new nodes like readers on the network side for device connectivity. The reader can be hosted at a traditional Base Station (BS), User Equipment (UE), or both, determining the specific supporting communication architecture for ENDS. Further, the data transmission procedures may need significant modification due to END's extremely limited capabilities and low reliability compared to devices supporting traditional broadband or vertical-specific use cases. From the perspective of data routing and forwarding, the END architecture can be categorized based on the following solutions [27]: user plane; control plane; and Radio Resource Control (RRC), which only applies to the case with a UE-based reader.

In the 3GPP RAN study on AIoT captured in TR 38.848 [1], four main deployment topologies are considered to support various communication and energy delivery mechanisms for AIoT devices:

- **BS - AIoT Device:** The device communicates directly with a BS, using a newly defined air interface. This is suitable for outdoor scenarios with sufficient BS coverage and energy provisioning.
- **BS - Intermediate Node - AIoT Device:** An intermediate node (e.g., relay, repeater) bridges communication between the BS and the device. This extends coverage and allows localized energy excitation.
- **BS - Assisting Node - AIoT Device - BS:** The device transmits data to a BS via one node (e.g., UE) and receives from another BS. This bidirectional split allows flexible pairing of RF energy source and data receiver/transmitter.
- **UE - AIoT Device:** A nearby UE (e.g., a phone, drone, or tractor) acts as both energy exciter and data collector, enabling completely localized and potentially offline AIoT operation, ideal for rural or infrastructure-sparse scenarios.

These topologies enable scalable and flexible AIoT deployment in both indoor and outdoor environments, balancing complexity, coverage, and energy availability.

¹Here, centralized, open or virtualized means how basedband unit operates if it is distributed, centralized, open or virtualized.

		F	#		#	
Memory categories						Volume
0	No Memory			0		<1 kB
1	RAM			1		1-64 kB
2	SRM			2		64-512 kB
3	ROM			3		512 kB-
						8 MB
				4		>8 MB

Figure 2.7: Categorization of memory categories and their corresponding volume levels.

2.1.6 Memory

The memory capabilities of IoT devices can be classified into four categories: **no memory**, **Random-Access Memory (RAM)**, **State-Retention Memory (SRM)**, and **Read-Only Memory (ROM)**, as captured in Figure 2.7.

Different memory types used in IoT devices are discussed below and summarized in Table 2.3.

2.1.6.1 No memory

This class includes ultra-passive devices such as chipless RFIDs. Even chipless devices can implement a form of data storage by leveraging physical-state mechanisms that enable permanent or extremely long-term retention without requiring power. In a broad sense, any enduring physical change that can be reliably read qualifies as non-volatile storage. This change can be made during the manufacturing or based on some dynamic event while in use.

In chipless RFID, the tag identity, a binary code, is stored in the physical property of the device. One such design uses multiple resonators, each tuned to a distinct frequency to implement the code: The presence or absence of a particular resonator represents binary data (1s and 0s). A reader transmits a wideband RF signal and detects the unique frequency response backscattering from the tag.

An example of physical change-based memory is **One-Time-Programmable (OTP)** memory, which relies on fuses that can be permanently altered by applying a high-current pulse. This process changes the state of the fuse, typically representing a binary 0 or 1 depending on whether the fuse remains intact or has been blown. Many MCUs integrate a small OTP memory bank using fuses, commonly for storing calibration data, encryption keys, device identity, or configuration flags. A purely analog device could also use OTP to permanently store information.

2.1.6.2 RAM

RAM is fast and byte-addressable, but it requires continuous power to retain data. The two main types are **Static RAM (SRAM)** and **Dynamic RAM (DRAM)**. SRAM stores each bit using a six-transistor latch, providing very fast access (often single-cycle latency) and no need for refresh, making it ideal for caches and on-chip memory where speed is critical. However, it has higher power consumption per bit and lower density due to its larger cell size. In contrast, DRAM stores data using a single transistor and capacitor per bit, making it much denser and cheaper per bit than SRAM, supporting capacities from megabytes to gigabytes. However, DRAM requires

periodic refresh (every few milliseconds) to prevent data loss, introducing additional power and latency overhead. SRAM is used in CPU caches, registers, and low-power MCUs, while DRAM is preferred for bulk memory in computers, mobile devices, and high-performance embedded systems.

2.1.6.3 SRM

SRM is a type of low-power volatile memory that preserves data during deep sleep or low-power modes by maintaining a minimal supply voltage. It bridges the gap between standard volatile RAM (which loses data when power is removed) and Non-Volatile Memory (NVM) by enabling devices to quickly resume operations without full system reinitialization. Typically implemented as low-leakage SRAM, SRM is used in MCUs and ultra-low-power IoT devices to store system state, sensor data, or execution context while consuming only microamps or less of standby power. This makes it ideal for battery-powered and EH systems, where frequent wake-up and state restoration must occur with minimal energy overhead. However, unlike true NVM such as Ferroelectric RAM (FRAM) or Flash, SRM still loses data if power is completely lost, making it suitable for power-managed sleep states but not for long-term storage.

2.1.6.4 ROM

ROM is a type of NVM that permanently stores data, retaining information even when power is removed. Unlike volatile RAM, ROM is primarily used for firmware storage, boot code, and system initialization, where data remains unchanged throughout the device's lifetime. Traditional mask ROM is programmed during manufacturing and cannot be modified, while more flexible types like Erasable Programmable ROM (EPROM), Electrically EPROM (EEPROM), and Flash memory allow reprogramming, though often with energy-intensive or slow write operations. Flash memory, a modern form of EEPROM, is widely used in embedded systems for firmware storage due to its high density and low cost per bit, though it suffers from limited endurance (10^4 – 10^6 write cycles) and high write energy consumption. ROM technologies are commonly found in MCUs, BIOS chips, and storage devices, ensuring that critical system data remain intact even after power loss.

This category often includes devices with enhanced security features, tightly integrated with the ROM to ensure integrity:

- **Trusted execution environments within ROM:** Secure areas, often implemented in conjunction with the ROM and CPU, that protect sensitive code and data from unauthorized access. These environments leverage the immutability of ROM to ensure the integrity of security-critical operations.
- **Tamper resistance in ROM:** Physical or logical mechanisms that prevent unauthorized modification of the firmware stored within the ROM, ensuring its integrity and preventing malicious attacks. This is often achieved through secure boot processes and hardware-based security features.
- **Secure boot from ROM:** Processes that verify the integrity of the firmware stored in ROM before execution, ensuring that only trusted code is run. This is a critical aspect of maintaining the security of devices relying primarily on ROM.

Table 2.3: Comparison of memory technologies.

Memory Type	Volatility	Read Speed (ns)	Write Speed (ns)	Endurance (Cycles)	Power Consumption	Typical Size
DRAM	Volatile	10–50	50–100	10^7 – 10^9	Moderate (refresh required)	MB–GB
SRAM	Volatile	<10	<10	Unlimited	High (static leakage)	kB–MB
FRAM	Non-Volatile	50–100	50–100	10^{12} – 10^{15}	Very Low	kB–MB
MRAM	Non-Volatile	20–40	20–100	10^{12} – 10^{15}	Low	kB–MB
Flash (NOR)	Non-Volatile	10–100	10^6 – 10^7	10^4 – 10^6	High (write/erase)	MB–GB
Flash (NAND)	Non-Volatile	†	10^6 – 10^7	10^4 – 10^6	High (write/erase)	MB–GB
SRM	State Retention	<10	<10	Unlimited	Low (retention current)	kB–MB

†) NAND flash read speeds are typically measured as the latency to access a page of data. Typical page access times are 10 μs to 50 μs.

2.1.6.5 NVM

Flash memory is a NVM technology that uses floating-gate transistors to store electrical charge, thereby representing data. It is organized into blocks, requiring erase operations before programming new data, and typically supports endurance in the range of 10^4 to 10^6 cycles. Although it offers high storage density and low cost per bit, flash memory exhibits slower write and erase speeds compared to volatile memory, and its operations necessitate higher voltage levels. These technical attributes make flash well-suited for firmware storage and applications where data is updated infrequently.

FRAM is a NVM technology that utilizes ferroelectric capacitors to store data, offering fast write speeds and low power consumption. Unlike flash memory, FRAM does not require an erase operation before writing new data, which significantly reduces write latency and energy usage. It supports a much higher number of write cycles—often ranging from 10^{12} to 10^{15} cycles—making it particularly suitable for applications that require frequent data updates. These technical characteristics enable FRAM to serve effectively in energy-constrained and intermittently powered systems, such as sensor nodes in IoT applications, where rapid data logging and durability are critical.

Magnetoresistive RAM (MRAM) is a NVM technology that uses magnetic tunnel junctions to store data. In MRAM, information is represented by the magnetic orientation of a ferromagnetic layer, which can be switched by applying a spin-polarized current. This mechanism enables fast read and write operations that are comparable to those of SRAM, while also retaining data without power. MRAM typically exhibits low power consumption, especially during write operations, and offers high endurance, often exceeding 10^{12} write cycles. Its non-destructive read capability and rapid access times facilitate direct code execution from memory, contributing to reduced system boot times and improved overall energy efficiency in embedded applications.

No Memory ⇒ Volume				
0	1	2	3	4

RAM ⇒ Volume				
0	1	2	3	4

SRM ⇒ Volume				
0	1	2	3	4

Table 2.4: Performance categories for the RF-powered Electronic Shelf Label (ESL) PoC.

Code	Description
A11	A screen update requires 75 mJ of energy. The minimum capacitance needed to store this amount of energy—considering a charging cut-off voltage of 3.1 V and a discharging cut-off voltage of 0.9 V—is 18 mF. For this PoC, an -aluminum electrolytic capacitor of 22 mF was selected.
B22	The required energy update is relatively high and difficult to harvest from an ambient source. In this PoC, an infrastructure with multiple antennas was assumed to provide the necessary RF-WPT signals.
C12	The e-paper display is directly connected to the microcontroller, and communication occurs via the SPI bus.
D200	The firmware on the STM32L031K6 executes sequential code to refresh the e-paper display as soon as it is powered on.
E110	This PoC focused solely on the energy aspect and demonstrating feasibility. The communication required for tasks such as adjusting the price was not implemented. In the final system, at least a downlink is required to receive and apply price updates. This can be integrated in a fully passive manner.
F11	External SRAM is used to store the updated bitmap before refreshing the SSD1680 e-paper display. Additionally, internal RAM is available within the MCU.
F21	Internal flash memory of the MCU.
F31	Internal EEPROM memory of the MCU is used to store the display frame number. Each time the MCU is powered on, a new bitmap is generated, such as one for a different price or product.

ROM ⇒ Volume				
0	1	2	3	4

2.2 Use case examples

This section clarifies and illustrates how the codes can be linked to an END design. In principle, six codes can be defined per design. However, in some applications, this number may be higher, as it is common for certain categories to define more than a single code, e.g., if both RAM and ROM are used in a certain application.

RF-powered ESL with COTS components: The Proof-of-Concept (PoC) from Figure 3.8 can harvest energy from 868 MHz to 920 MHz RF bands and store the energy in a capacitor. In a second step, the e-paper display is refreshed relying solely on the stored energy [28]. A more detailed explanation can be found in Section 3.2.2. Its classification in performance categories is clarified in Table 2.4.

NFC-based passive flow sensor for smart silos: This is a totally passive sensor that relies on Near-Field Communication (NFC) for power transfer during operation. On-board is a unique ID (UID), identifying the silo as well as real-time readout of a flow sensor. This prototype is further elaborated upon in Section 3.1.2 on page 27, its classification in performance categories is clarified in Table 2.5 on the following page.

Table 2.5: Performance categories for the NFC-based passive flow sensor for smart silos.

Code	Description
A0	No onboard energy storage.
B33	Powered via NFC, which utilizes inductive WPT through a coupled magnetic field.
C23	Flow sensor (connected to an ADC to monitor animal feed in the supply pipe to the silo).
D300	Small Arm Cortex-M0+ MCU to coordinate sensing.
E312	Communication is handled through the NFC link.
F21	Internal RAM memory of the MCU.
F31	Internal flash memory of the MCU.
F31	Internal EEPROM memory buffer of the NFC tag IC.

Table 2.6: Performance categories for a standing water monitoring on rooftops prototype IoT device.

Code	Description
A37	Powered through 2 (rechargeable) AA batteries.
B11	Rechargeable through a solar panel array (potential extension to the prototype).
C25	Level sensors to sense the presence of standing water.
D312	Processing is done through an Arm Cortex-M33, which is the onboard application processor in the SPI nRF9160. The application alarms the user based on the state of water level. To facilitate secure firmware updates, hardware layer security is added.
E312	Communication is handled through a NB-IoT link.
F22	Internal RAM memory of the MCU.
F33	Internal flash memory of the MCU.

Standing water monitoring on rooftops to ensure structural integrity: This is a sensor that detects standing water using up to four rooftop-mounted water probes, transmitting alerts and periodic status updates. This prototype is powered by internal batteries with the optional extension for solar EH. This IoT device is further elaborated upon in Section 3.3.2 on page 39, its classification in performance categories is clarified in Table 2.6.

Other END class applicability scenarios Different END capability classes may apply to other AMBIENT-6G use cases, such as the ones of smart end-to-end logistics and collaborative mobile robots. First, with respect to energy storage RFID tags (A00), the end-to-end logistics use case is of relevance, e.g., involving item (container) pick and place operations. Regarding END energy scavenging/ harvesting capability, when it comes to scavenging energy - B14 - B17 category ENDS can be used within an industrial setting (e.g., factory floor), as such environment is expected to be rich in industrial noise and vibrations as well as heat, depending on the specific area of END placement. B17 - B19 ENDS can be deployed as part of an agricultural/ aquacultural environment that can be windy on the ground or of high water flow density, respectively.

Considering ENDS classified as having uncoupled WPT capabilities, RF-WPT (B22) ENDS are

relevant, as suitable for indoor environments with no or low opportunities to scavenge ambient energy. These devices can be placed onboard collaborative mobile robots, thanks to connectivity to access points (APs), possibly collocated with a robot route (or task) controller. The applicable environment can be, for example, the one of automated warehouse. Since dedicated RF signals (for example, reference signals in a cellular deployment) are used to target ENds of this capability, such ENds can also be deployed in a road environment, for example, onboard trucks and forklifts as part of a smart end-to-end logistics scenario.

Regarding END interface capabilities, no interface ENds (C0 or C00) corresponding to RFID tags can be used within a smart end-to-end logistics setting, while bus interfaces (C11) which, with proper design, can be used over the wireless medium (e.g. PROFINET [29]) may apply to use cases involving collaborative mobile robots (e.g., manufacturing robots on a factory floor). In addition, RF interfaces used for the needs of device positioning and creation of a digital twin of a physical environment can enable the detection of presence in an area for both route (re)planning and facility security purposes.

Some END capability classes may be more preferable than others depending on their supported communication interface and signaling activity level. For instance, focusing on the smart end-to-end logistics use case, both passive and active ENds communicating through the RF medium apply to such scenarios involving, for example, a fleet of vehicles to support product or material delivery tasks. In this case, the passive devices can be used for smart tagging purposes (e.g., on a product or container), while, the active ones can be used for telematics data collection and upload to an edge server, e.g., for smart delivery task allocation or predictive vehicle maintenance purposes.

Finally, when it comes to processing and memory capabilities of ENds, ENds of limited such capabilities which can be deployed at large scale can better fit the purpose of data generation and transfer to a more powerful entity (e.g., another device of more advanced processing and memory capability) or, for example, an edge cloud server at network infrastructure side. On the contrary, ENds of higher such capability can serve as data aggregation nodes and support local decision making or even planning. Therefore, they are more relevant to multi-agent settings, such as collaborative mobile robots addressing the same task or robots performing different tasks, as part of an overall productivity goal.

Chapter 3

Device Classes

This chapter introduces four broad END classes and discusses their distinguishing feature, architectural and operational properties, and some existing prototypes and case studies. Note that although six performance categories were introduced in Chapter 2, the classification here weighs more the energy storage capability of the ENDS as this further dictates the type of operation that the peripheral, processing, communication, and memory capabilities of an END can perform, hence its cruciality in all ENDS. For example, it is unlikely that an END without meaningful energy storage can operate uninterruptedly since the incoming energy is usually random. An overview of the proposed ENDS classes with their energy storage and supported communication types is provided in Table 3.1 on the next page.

3.1 Ultra-passive

Distinguishing Feature(s): *No meaningful energy storage beyond transient circuit-level capacitance.*

3.1.1 Architectural and operational properties

UP ENDS are the simplest form of ENDS. They can only function while being illuminated by an external energy/signal source. Since they do not retain energy, their operation is strictly instantaneous and power/signal-dependent, meaning they cease to function immediately when the external power source or triggering signal is removed. Their capabilities are inherently limited to basic identification, signal reflection/modulation, and minimal sensing, relying on passive interactions such as backscattering, reflection, or structural resonance. Examples of UP ENDS include basic RFID tags, and metasurfaces, including passive reflective surfaces used in wireless communication and sensing applications. UP ENDS have near-zero maintenance needs, extreme longevity, and minimal fabrication complexity. A high-level block diagram for UP ENDS is provided in Figure 3.1.

Energy: The energy needs of these ENDS, if any, are met mainly by RF-EH. As these devices do not have an energy storage capability, the harvested energy cannot be used at a later stage. To stabilize the use of available energy for their instantaneous operations, it is possible that UP ENDS are equipped with tiny transient capacitors.

Table 3.1: Overview of the proposed ENDS classification.

END class	Type of energy storage	Type of communication support	Prototypes: classification codes
UP END	no or minimal storage	reflection based communication support	i) "Iridescent" reflective tags to enable radar-based orientation estimation: A00-B00/B12-C00-D000-E000-F00, ii) NFC-based passive flow sensor for smart silos: A0-B33-C23-D300-E342-F11/F31, iii) RFID sensor system using a tag antenna as sensing device: A0-B12-C00-D000-E112-F30, iv) Light-controlled BD for hybrid VLC/RF network: A00/A11-B11-C00-D000-E112/E122-F00.
DB END	tiny supercapacitor	intermittent communication	i) RF-powered ESL: A11-B22-C12-D210-E110-F11/F21/F31, ii) Hybrid RF indoor positioning system: A10-B22-C25/C27-D000-E112-F00, iii) RFID based passive distributed control for a RIS: A13-B11-C11-D412-E110/E220-F22/F32, iv) 2.45 GHz RF-EH device: (partial code) B12/B22, v) Measurement setup for wideband backscatter channel estimation: (partial code) E11-B22.
DP END	small battery or robust supercapacitors	intermittent but reliable communication	i) A low-power AmBC device based on MCU timer management: A13- B11-C11-D412-E110-F22/F32, ii) Standing water monitoring on rooftops to ensure structural integrity: A37-B11-C25-D312-E312-F12/F33
CO END	battery	active communication	i) Light-controlled BD with VLC-decode and RF-forward capability (Li2BC): A23-B11-C11-D412-E213/E223-F32, ii) Outdoor batteryless tracker: A26-B11/B12-C11/C23-D550-E314-F13/F22.

Typical Functions: UP-ENDs can only provide limited functionality, mainly relying on reflection and scattering. Other useful functions, such as Physical Unclonable Functions (PUFs)¹ and passive sensing, can be realized by utilizing the material properties.

Communication: UP ENDS rely on secondary RF transmissions to communicate their data, either using Backscatter Communications (BCs) or leveraging their physical structure/construction to convey a message, e.g., an identifier.

Security: The security features for UP ENDS rely on their structural/material properties and hence require precise fabrication techniques. At a basic level, PUFs can be used for the identification of these devices. However, challenge-response-based authentication mechanisms can also be implemented by altering the device's impedance state dynamically.

¹Note that for this END class, PUFs requiring any kind of processing can not be implemented due to insufficient energy availability.

Figure 3.1: High-level block diagram of a UP END: (left) END with transient level energy storage capability; and (right) END with no energy storage at all, where the presence/absence of reflected energy can, e.g., convey orientation of the object.

Applications: UP ENDs mainly provide passive support to IoT applications. For instance, UP ENDs in the form of passive reflectors can improve the channel quality for the link between transmitter and receiver through passive beamforming. Other common applications for these ENDs include localization, Radar Cross Section (RCS) tuning, identification/authentication, and environmental and structural monitoring.

3.1.2 Prototypes and case studies

“Iridescent” reflective tags to enable radar-based orientation estimation: The concept of tags with a frequency-selective angular response property is proposed and discussed in [30]. These tags have maximal reflected energy in a sub-band of the received wavefront spectrum. Such “iridescent” reflective tags are UP ENDs and can be used to assist robots in visually challenging environments, e.g., in situations where visibility is limited due to, e.g., smoke or fog, as shown in Figure 3.2. The tags merely reflect the impinging RF waves, and the radiating entity (mobile robots in this case) can infer relevant information (such as position, orientation etc) from the reflected waves.

The working principle of an “iridescent” reflective tag is shown in Figure 3.3: a radar (e.g., equipped on the robots in Figure 3.2), illuminates the tags with different frequency transmissions and based on the reflected signals decides on the orientation of the tag, and potentially that of the object it is attached to. These tags can be constructed using Leaky-Wave Antenna (LWA) technology. In such a case, some minimal RF-EH circuitry is needed for feeding. Therefore, and according to the framework in Chapter 2, the formal classification code of such LWA-based UP END is **A00-B00/B12²-C00-D000-E000-F00**.

NFC-based passive flow sensor for smart silos: To refill a silo with animal feed, a trailer with multiple compartments is connected to the silo using a filling tube. The feed is then blown through the tube and into the silo. Such a system, illustrated in Figure 3.4, is deployed to verify both the correct feed type is dispensed from the appropriate trailer compartment into the correct silo and that the feed flow is properly tracked. The system utilizes NFC technology, consisting of an NFC reader mounted on the trailer and a passive NFC sensor embedded in the silo, which is an UP END.

The NFC sensor operates without an internal power source, relying entirely on the electromagnetic field of the NFC reader for activation. When the NFC reader (which communicates with

²The exact choice of B00 or B12 is dependent on the use of LWA.

Figure 3.2: Use case for "Iridescent" reflective tags.

Figure 3.3: Working principle of "Iridescent" reflective tags.

the trailer) is positioned correctly in front of the sensor embedded in the silo, the sensor functions as an NFC tag and powers up its onboard MCU. The MCU then loads a unique identification code into the NFC memory buffer, allowing the system to verify which silo is being filled and whether the correct trailer compartment is being used. Additionally, the prototype integrates a flow sensor (analog based, read through an ADC) that begins measuring feed flow as soon as the trailer starts dispensing. This flow data is also stored in the NFC memory buffer, making it accessible to the NFC reader. The system continuously updates as long as it remains powered by the reader, enabling real-time tracking of flow rate. By eliminating the need for energy storage and relying entirely on NFC for power delivery, the embedded sensor is completely maintenance-free and can be seamlessly embedded into a silo in a weatherproof manner. Since there are no batteries to replace or exposed power contacts, the system remains durable and well-protected against environmental conditions.

According to the framework in Chapter 2, the formal classification code of this prototype is **A0-B33-C23-D300-E342-F11/F31**³.

RFID sensor system using a tag antenna as sensing device: The prototype created by Görtschacher *et al.* [31] presents a RFID sensor in the Ultra-High Frequency (UHF) domain that helps detect the fill level of a water canister based on the backscattered transponder signals of

³Microcontroller memory includes both RAM and ROM.

Figure 3.4: NFC-based passive flow sensor for smart silos: (left) the concept of the smart filling of silos; and (right) the NFC reader that connects to the passive tag with sensing element.

Figure 3.5: Schematic overview and measurement setup of the RFID sensor tag for detecting the water level of a water canister based on the backscattered transponder signal of the sensor tag (adapted from [31]).

the sensor tag, as illustrated in Figure 3.5. This is achieved by exploiting changes in the tag's impedance coming from external stimuli, like variations in water level in this example. These impedance changes affect the backscattered signal received by the RFID reader. By processing these signal variations, the system can deduce the corresponding environmental conditions. This approach maintains the passive nature of the RFID tags, ensuring low-maintenance and cost-effective sensing capabilities.

As the sensing capabilities of the device come from the backscattered response, the RFID sensor (with NXP UCODE 7 IC [32]) must be seen as an UP-END, which can be classified as **A0-B12-C00-D000-E112-F30**.

Light-controlled BD for hybrid VLC/RF network: A light-controlled BC system is proposed in [33] to integrate VLC and Ambient BC (AmBC) for future ambient power-enabled IoT. A Backscatter Device (BD), named LiBD, utilizes light signals for both backscatter modulation control and energy supply. LiBD contains a light harvester and backscatter modulator. The synergy between VLC and AmBC with LiBD is illustrated in Figure 3.6. The light harvester collects and converts the modulated light signal into electrical signals for both controlling the modulation and powering the device. With the control signals, the modulator modulates the ambient carrier waves by alternating its reflection coefficients. The modulated signals are then

backscattered and can be captured by receivers equipped with RF front-ends. The LiBD serves as a bridge or relay between VLC and AmBC networks.

The fusion of advanced device packaging and integration technologies enabled by the additive manufacturing of RF components with low-cost inkjet printing method was considered for the fabrication of the LiBD. A compact thin-film LiBD [34], shown in Figure 3.6 was proposed and manufactured for receiving VLC signal from Light Emitting Diodes (LEDs) and relaying them to RF receivers at the 2.4 GHz Industrial, Scientific and Medical (ISM) band. Benefiting from additive manufacturing methods with Commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) materials, the inkjet-printed circuit board, antenna, and lumped components are integrated on flexible Polyethylene Terephthalate (PEET) substrates for realizing the device functionalities, including light harvest, and RF modulation and reflection.

According to the framework in Chapter 2, the formal classification code of this prototype is **A00/A11-B11-C00-D000-E112/E122-F00**.

3.2 Duty-cycled barebone

Distinguishing Feature(s): *Presence of short-term energy storage to power operations in a duty-cycled manner.*

3.2.1 Architectural and operational properties

DB ENDS extend the basic functionality of the UP END class by introducing a small, short-term energy buffer in the form of capacitors or tiny supercapacitors. This allows the device to accumulate minimal amounts of power and operate intermittently in short bursts, e.g., performing basic on-device sensing, rudimentary data processing, or brief communication tasks on a duty-cycled schedule. Their operation is not necessarily instantaneously triggered by RF illumination. Examples include smart labels that log environmental conditions (e.g., temperature or humidity), simple wearable health tags that periodically check vital signs, and ultra-low-power sensor nodes for industrial or agricultural monitoring. While slightly more complex than UP ENDS, DB ENDS are still low-maintenance and have long operational lifetimes and modest fabrication

Figure 3.6: Light-controlled BD for a hybrid VLC/RF network.

Figure 3.7: High-level block diagram of a DB END.

costs, making them ideal for cost-effective, semi-autonomous IoT solutions. A high-level block diagram for DB ENDs is provided in Figure 3.7.

Energy: In contrast to UP ENDs where energy could not be stored for later use, a short-term energy storage either using small capacitors or supercapacitors is available for DB ENDs. Thus, energy does not have to be consumed instantaneously but it can be rather accumulated for short burst operation. Typical energy sources for this END class include RF, small solar cells, piezoelectric harvesters, and thermoelectric gradients.

Typical Functions: DB ENDs can perform some basic functions, such as sensing and data processing. Examples of sensing can include, among others, temperature and humidity measurements. On the other hand, data processing examples can include basic filtering or threshold detection. These functions can be activated either by some event (event-driven) or periodic signal (periodic-activation). Indeed, energy preservation mechanisms are used to keep the device at a low or no-power state most of the time while waking it up briefly to perform a task.

Communication: Although energy storage is possible for devices in this class, the communication is still predominantly passive, i.e., backscattering-based, or semi-passive, i.e., supporting low-power active communication, depending on energy buffer and energy dimensioning. Additionally, the supported transmission has low-throughput and uses communication in bursts, i.e., transmit quickly and go dormant.

Security: Since DB ENDs can implement some basic data processing functions, the challenge-response mechanisms in this class do not need to rely solely on the device's impedance state, as for the UP ENDs. Indeed, they can adopt simple challenge-response mechanisms if the hardware allows brief computation. Furthermore, DB ENDs may also store small cryptographic keys in NVM for authentication.

Applications: Similar to UP ENDs, DB ENDs mainly provide passive support to IoT applications, but wherein the former fail due to their rather stringent constraints. This includes DB ENDs as smart labels for inventory and logistics, wearable health tags, and environmental sensors in industrial or agricultural monitoring.

Figure 3.8: Prototype of the proposed ESL architecture. The black box in the upper right corner includes two connectors, allowing real-time voltage monitoring of the capacitor.

3.2.2 Prototypes and case studies

RF-powered ESL: A batteryless ESL powered by RF-WPT using COTS components is explored in [28]. The proposed ESL design is validated through a dedicated testbed and involves a detailed analysis of design choices, including energy consumption, energy conversion, and storage solutions. A leaded aluminium electrolytic capacitor is selected as the primary energy storage element, balancing cost and performance while maintaining compactness. Experimental evaluations demonstrate that an ESL can update its display within 4 to 120 minutes, depending on input power and RF frequency, with harvester efficiencies reaching up to 30%. Challenges such as low harvester efficiency, extended update times, and hardware constraints are identified, highlighting opportunities for future optimizations. This prototype provides valuable insights into system design considerations for RF-powered ESLs and establishes a foundation for new research in energy-neutral IoT applications. An illustration of the prototype is shown in Figure 3.8.

According to the framework in Chapter 2, the formal classification code of this prototype is **A11-B22-C12-D210-E110-F11⁴/F21/F31**.

Hybrid RF indoor positioning system: A low-power, hybrid RF-acoustic mobile node that performs frequency shifted, load switching backscattering of acoustic chirp fragments for indoor positioning. The zero-crossing, combined RF and acoustic indoor positioning approach is detailed in [35]. In a nutshell, RF signals are used for synchronization and communication (by means of backscattering) and distances, thus the actual position, are obtained by pulse compressing short samples of slower propagating acoustic chirp signals.

An overview of the used hardware is depicted in Figure 3.9 and can be divided into two parts: the acoustic section in which the analog, ultrasound signals are captured and transformed via zero-crossing into a digitized version, and the RF section, which backscatters these digital signals through switching the load of the antenna.

The acoustic section consists of (I) micro-electromechanical systems (MEMS) microphone (Ves-

⁴In addition to the internal RAM of the MCU, external RAM is utilized in this PoC to temporarily store the bitmap.

Figure 3.9: Block diagram and Printed Circuit Board (PCB) layout of the backscatter module.

per VM1000) with a low-power consumption, short wake-up time (below $200 \mu\text{s}$), high sensitivity, and wide frequency response. In-house measurements show that frequencies over 80 kHz can be received sufficiently, much higher than stated in the audible domain-focused datasheet. (II) Amplifier (TI TLV341) with low-noise amplifier has a high UGB, amplifying and filtering the signal before zero-crossing it by the (III) comparator (TI TLV7031).

In the RF section, the output of the comparator containing the digitized microphone signal is connected to an SPDT-switch (AD ADG839). This acts as a multiplexer, passing either the local oscillator signal (AD LTC6906) with a frequency of f_{clo} or a low-voltage signal. The local oscillator frequency is set with two resistors, and can take values between 10 kHz and 1 MHz . Implementing double sideband modulation, a total bandwidth of 80 kHz can be accommodated, defined by the maximum chirp frequency ($f_{a,max} = 40 \text{ kHz}$). Next, this frequency modulated signal is fed into the RF load switches (ADG904). An external dipole PCB antenna connected to the antenna port of the backscatter module, consists of two $\lambda/4$ copper strips with a small gap between them. For this antenna at least two load switches are required to correctly short and open these two sides. The ADG904 has four multiplexer channels. This means there are two more multiplexer inputs available on both of these chips. This makes it possible for other resistors, inductors and capacitors to be used as a complex, serial load between the two copper traces, enabling additional antenna loads for improved reading distance.

The backscattered acoustic signals are captured by receivers at the central system and further processed by means of pulse compression to obtain the ranging information and eventual location.

Note that an Low-Dropout Voltage Regulator (LDO) voltage converter is missing from the schematic overview in Figure 3.9 (left figure) but can be found in the PCB design Figure 3.9 (right figure). This LDO regulator converts a higher input voltage coming from an energy buffer into a lower voltage for a DC-offset in the acoustic signal and powers the low-voltage components.

For complete energy-neutral operation, the current hardware should be extended with an EH circuit, e.g. E-Peas AEM 40940, and an RF wake-up detector for synchronized wake-ups. These components are grayed out as these are not integrated yet in the current hardware.

According to the framework in Chapter 2, the formal classification code of this prototype for each performance category is **A10-B22-C25/C27-D000-E112-F00**.

Figure 3.10: Schematic overview of the RIS END with all main components insights on the ambient light EH power supply. The dark green block highlights the energy harvesting section, while the light green blocks are required for control and configuration of the RIS.

RFID based passive distributed control for a RIS: A Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface (RIS) is a controllable surface that can redirect and manipulate electromagnetic waves in wireless communication and WPT systems. A RIS prototype as an DB END is developed in [36] and illustrated here in Figure 3.10. Such a device leverages ambient light to power the controller board together with a supercapacitor with a capacity of 2.2 J. An RFID tag is used for communication to get the required control signals to the RIS, which wakes the control device up and therefore enables a reconfiguration cycle to happen (duty-cycle based reconfiguration). The controller board is equipped with a MCU (Atmega4809) to process the data coming from the RFID tag and to control all the RF switches for the antenna elements on the RIS.

According to the framework in Chapter 2, the formal classification code of this prototype is **A13-B11-C11-D412-E110/E220⁵-F22/F32⁶**.

2.45 GHz RF-EH device: The device presented in Figure 3.11 offers a detailed analysis of a test IC, originally designed for operation in the UHF RFID band at 900 MHz, with a specific emphasis on its performance at 2.45 GHz. This frequency falls within the commonly utilized 2.4 GHz to 2.5 GHz ISM band, where many consumer devices with wireless communication protocols like WiFi, Bluetooth or Zigbee are operated [37].

The device is not an END prototype itself but a tool to evaluate the charge pump integrated within the test IC, which plays a crucial role in efficiently converting received RF energy into usable DC electrical power. A Power Conversion Efficiency (PCE) of 11.6 % was attained using the antenna illustrated in Figure 3.11, while a PCE of up to 25.9 % could be realized with optimized antenna's matching [37]. The test IC analysis highlights its capability to be used in ENDS, which require RF energy as their power input.

The device was further utilized for RF-WPT experiments in a real-world office environment, focusing on the harvestable power with beamforming established by a LTE Multiple-Input Multiple-Output (MIMO) Base Transceiver Station (BTS), as illustrated in Figure 3.13. For these ex-

⁵Backscatter TX, VLC RX

⁶MCU internal 256 kB retained SRAM, 512 kB FLASH

Figure 3.11: Harvested power analysis device (microPowerProfiler on the left) together with the RF-EH test IC on a daughter-board (on the right) with a custom-designed dipole antenna for 2.45 GHz.

periments, another antenna setup was used, where the RF port of the test IC was matched to a Sub-Miniature Version A (SMA) connector. The latter was then further connected to a standard dipole WiFi antenna, often used for access points and WiFi routers.

The setup is schematically depicted in Figure 3.12. The transmit beam of the BTS is steered towards a fixed point in space using the uplink pilots of an LTE UE, while the END is moved over space and its DC output power measured. The BTS and UE use a Time Division Duplexing (TDD) LTE signal at 2.44 GHz with 20 MHz of bandwidth. The resulting power distribution along the physical lab setup is shown in Figure 3.13.

A formal classification code according to the framework from Chapter 2 for the entire prototype/ENDs used in this case study is not applicable. The demonstrated concept enables devices to be powered by RF energy harvesting and are then classified with the sub-category **B12** or **B22**. Other classification codes depend on the specific implementation of further concepts or features.

Measurement setup for wideband backscatter channel estimation: A PoC measurement setup is built for wideband bistatic backscatter scenarios as depicted by Figure 3.14. It is used to validate the algorithm proposed in [38], which features the following points crucial to wideband backscatter systems in general: i) estimation of wideband Channel State Information (CSI) from bistatic backscatter systems; ii) mitigation of the strong DLI inherent to bistatic backscatter systems; iii) estimation of the unknown backscatter modulation parameters of the END for synchronization. The estimated CSI enables positioning of the END, improves the WPT, and enables a robust communication. The algorithm can use arbitrary TX signals, e.g. ambient OFDM.

Figure 3.15 shows the actual measurement setup. A wideband transceiver is implemented using an SDR. The TX signal of the SDR is split up in two paths, one is directly routed back and the remaining one is dedicated to the backscattering END.

The END is connected to the splitter using a long coaxial cable to introduce a significant

Figure 3.12: Schematic overview of the WPT measurement setup.

Figure 3.13: Measurement setup with the layout of the laboratory, where the RF-EH device was positioned to measure the received power from the BTS with fixed beamforming over a specified area.

propagation delay. A variable RF attenuator is inserted to set the Signal-to-Interference Ratio (SIR) of the backscatter channel.

For the END, an ADG918 Complementary Metal Oxide Semiconductor (CMOS)-based RF switch from Analog Devices is used together with an evaluation board and external impedances. The PWM signal switching the END impedances is produced by an arbitrary waveform generator. For the practical implementation of the impedance modulation in an actual END, minimal energy storage beyond circuit-level capacitance is required. The framework can therefore be attributed to this device class.

This setup can be modified or extended (e.g., to transmit wirelessly or to a MIMO transceiver) to produce measurement data to validate potential algorithms for wideband CSI estimation and BC in WP3.

A formal classification code according to the classification introduced in Chapter 2 for the prototype/ENDs used in this case study is not applicable. The concepts or features evaluated may be applicable to different categories. A classification depends on the specific implementation

Figure 3.14: System model: An Orthogonal Frequency-Division Multiplexing (OFDM) signal transmitted from the Transmitter (TX) impinges at the Receiver (RX) as the sum of the strong Direct Link Interference (DLI) with several multipath components and the weak backscatter modulated signal from the END.

Figure 3.15: Wired setup for bistatic backscatter measurement using a Software-Defined Radio (SDR). The SDR is connected to a resistive splitter with two coaxial cables. Signals in the backscatter path are attenuated by a variable RF attenuator. The Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) switching signal is generated by an arbitrary waveform generator.

of the concept or feature. However, the setup presented can be used to test and emulate **E11**-classified devices, and in combination with suitable detection and estimation algorithms, it can be used to emulate a WPT system for class **B22**-classified devices in a MIMO configuration.

3.3 Duty-cycled persistent

Distinguishing Feature(s): *Presence of long-term rechargeable energy storage and persistent operation according to schedules/duty-cycles.*

3.3.1 Architectural and operational properties

DP ENDs, as opposed to DB ENDs, benefit from small, rechargeable energy storage (e.g., a small battery or robust supercapacitor), allowing them to run persistently on scheduled duty cycles while saving/recovering states from memory if needed. The expanded energy budget lets them handle moderate sensing tasks, maintain basic data logging, and even perform low-complexity actuation. By buffering enough power between cycles, these devices can regularly wake to measure environmental parameters, store or process data (including intermittent computing), and communicate using backscattering or low-power active protocols. These devices balance autonomy and energy efficiency, making them suitable for more advanced industrial IoT applications, agricultural monitoring, and biomedical sensors that need intermittent but reliable operation. Expect these devices to be more adaptive and versatile compared to lower-class ENDs. A high-level block diagram for DP ENDs is provided in Figure 3.16.

Figure 3.16: High-level block diagram of DP END.

Energy: DP ENDS have long-term energy storage capability in the form of a sufficiently large supercapacitor or even a small rechargeable battery. Energy storage allows energy accumulation to handle scheduled duty cycles and maintain regular or event-driven wake cycles for moderate-complexity tasks. The most commonly used energy sources for DP END include small solar cells, thermoelectric gradients, dedicated RF, kinetic/vibration, piezoelectric, and electrodynamic.

Typical Functions: In addition to the typical functionalities of the DB ENDS (i.e. sensing and data processing), DP ENDS can also provide moderate on-device operations such as low-complexity actuation, data aggregation from multiple sensors, and low-complexity local decision-making. They may recover computation/data states using intermittent computation techniques.

Communications: DP ENDS can support passive or low-power active communication, the latter being more common than for previous END classes. More heterogeneous traffic modes and higher bit rates, compared to previous END classes, are supported.

Security: DP ENDS may support lightweight cryptographic and authentication measures, e.g., simple challenge-response protocols or key-based authentication. It is also possible to integrate PUF by storing PUF-based or material-based signatures with added capability to handle queries through basic logic. Finally, the NVM allows the device to retain credentials or encryption keys between cycles.

Applications: DP ENDS fit i) precision agriculture, by continuously monitoring soil moisture, temperature, and crop health with minimal power consumption; ii) industrial settings, by tracking machinery performance and environmental conditions, reducing maintenance costs and downtime; and iii) wearable biomedical applications, by reliably recording vital signs over extended periods. Moreover, their energy-efficient design and adaptive functionality make them excellent candidates for smart infrastructure and critical monitoring systems in various sectors.

DB ENDS and DP ENDS may enable indoor proximity-based positioning. For instance, these devices can intermittently activate to measure signal strength or phase differences, accurately estimating their positions relative to one another [39]. This approach enables robust asset tracking and navigation within indoor environments, all while consuming minimal power. With the help of existing ambient signals, such systems offer a scalable, low-cost solution for smart

Figure 3.17: A low-power AmBC device based on MCU timer management.

buildings, industrial facilities, and other applications where traditional localization methods may be impractical.

3.3.2 Prototypes and case studies

A low-power AmBC device based on MCU timer management: An DP END using AmBC is proposed and illustrated in Figure 3.17, which was used for AmBC experiments in [40]. A low-power operation is achieved using MCU timer management. The main device components include a low-power energy harvester ADP5091, an MCU STM32L562, and a backscatter modulator tag based on an RF switch ADG919. The energy harvester converts and stores power from a Photovoltaic (PV) cell to a set of supercapacitors. The MCU uses a low-power timer to generate the PWM signal. By keeping the PWM signal duty cycle at 50 % and changing the signal frequency, a Binary Frequency Shift Keying (BFSK) modulation can be implemented. Another timer is used for symbol timing. The used timers can run independently while the MCU is in a low-power state. The MCU can be kept in a low-power state for the duration of one symbol and only be woken up to set the timers for a new symbol. Thus, for most of the transmission time, the MCU is in a low-power state. Running from 3.3 V source the MCU uses on average $6.6 \mu\text{A}$ current ($22 \mu\text{W}$) during the transmission with 40 ms symbol length. A 35 mm \times 21 mm solar panel can keep the device running on normal indoor office lightning. Four 0.1 F supercapacitors are used for energy storage. The storage is enough to keep the device running for 36 hours with a 10-second transmission interval.

The backscatter modulator tag employs an RF switch connected to the antenna, switching its termination between open and short condition. The switch control signal, i.e., baseband backscatter signal, is generated from the MCU, and BFSK is utilized here. Hence, the switching speed changes between two predefined frequencies. When the ambient RF signal illuminates the antenna, it gets mixed with the control signal by the switching. The mixed signals reflect to the reader, which detects and demodulates the reflected signals to recover the carried information.

According to the framework in Chapter 2, the formal classification of this prototype is **A13-B11-C11-D412-E110-F22/F32**⁷.

⁷MCU internal 256 kB retained SRAM, 512 kB FLASH

Standing water monitoring on rooftops to ensure structural integrity: If a flat roof lacks a proper system to expel water, water may accumulate there, causing the rooftop to overflow. This not only presents potential water damage concerns but can also lead to more serious structural stability problems. To address this, a prototype has been developed specifically to monitor water levels on large industrial rooftops. This monitoring system is equipped with a MCU, an NB-IoT modem for communication, a Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) sensor for precise location tracking, and, most importantly, multiple water level sensors — with the ability to incorporate up to four individual sensors.

The current prototype is designed to be entirely powered via a non-rechargeable battery and consequently does not classify as a END. The water level sensors continuously measure the rise of water on the rooftop in a low-power manner. In the event that the water level reaches predefined alarm thresholds, the NB-IoT modem will send an immediate notification. Additionally, a daily keep-alive message is transmitted to confirm the system's operational status and provide additional monitoring data.

This prototype will be expanded in WP4 and WP5 to incorporate EH, turning it into an DP END. Solar EH will be explored to supplement the system's power needs. Additionally, the detection system may be upgraded with camera-based monitoring and ML algorithms to enable more intelligent alerting of abnormal roof conditions.

According to the framework in Chapter 2, the formal classification code of the DP END prototype that is to be developed is **A37-B11-C25-D312-E312-F12/F33**⁸.

3.4 Continuous-operation

Distinguishing Feature(s): *Presence of long-term rechargeable energy storage that allows sustaining (semi-)continuous operation.*

3.4.1 Architectural and operational properties

CO ENDs represent the most capable category of ENDs, featuring robust or continuous EH and sufficiently large rechargeable storage to avoid interruptions caused by power failures, including advanced computation/processing features. They typically support active communication protocols, making them highly suitable for smart city applications, predictive industrial maintenance, and autonomous environmental monitoring. CO ENDs are expected to function autonomously, self-adapt to changing conditions, and integrate more advanced analytics such as ML inference, all while remaining energy-neutral. They bridge the gap between energy-efficient IoT and fully autonomous wireless systems. A high-level block diagram for CO ENDs is provided in Figure 3.18.

Energy: CO ENDs harvest energy from either a single high-power EH source or multiple sources, such as solar, thermal, and/or vibration, and store it in a long-term energy storage. Furthermore, these devices may also include smart power controllers to dynamically allocate energy among different types of tasks, e.g., computation, sensing, communication, and actuation.

⁸Microcontroller memory includes both RAM and ROM.

Figure 3.18: High-level block diagram of a CO END.

Typical Functions: CO ENDs can perform moderate to high on-device operations such as sensing, data processing, real-time low-complexity actuation, data fusion, and even local ML inference. In addition, the moderate-to-high onboard logic for processing can be used to perform self-monitoring and adaptive scheduling.

Communication: CO ENDs may maintain active communication, including frequent and/or real-time data transmission, and implement adaptive communication protocols, e.g., based on channel conditions, frequency/time resource availability, etc.

Security: CO ENDs support secure firmware updates, mutual authentication with gateways, and intrusion detection, for example, through anomaly-based monitoring. In addition to these network-based security procedures, CO ENDs can also run AI-based threat detection or anomaly detection locally, thus safeguarding the device and network in real time.

Applications: Generally, CO ENDs have their applications in smart city infrastructure, and predictive industrial maintenance. Furthermore, properties such as hybrid EH and smart power controllers make them suitable for environmental monitoring, wildlife monitoring, high-end wearables, and healthcare devices.

3.4.2 Prototypes and case studies

Light-controlled BD with VLC-decode and RF-forward capability (Li2BC): A CO END using light-controlled BC with light-decoding and RF-forwarding capability, named Li2BC, is proposed in [41] and illustrated in Figure 3.19. The device integrates VLC signal receiving, processing, and RF backscatter modulation functionalities. By utilizing a low-power MCU, the Li2BC can receive, amplify, demodulate, and store/cache VLC signals. This caching capability enables the device to store VLC data for subsequent control of backscatter operations, enhancing its configurability and flexibility.

The Li2BC is powered by a PV cell, which is also used to receive control data over light. As the information is encoded in a high-frequency component, it can be extracted by filtering. The filtered signal is then amplified and fed into the MCU for backscatter control. The MCU communicates with BD-embedded sensors, acquiring sensing data periodically. To transmit the data with AmBC, Li2BC uses one of the MCU's timers to generate frequencies for BFSK

Figure 3.19: Light-controlled BD with VLC-decode and RF-forward capability (Li2BC).

modulation. The MCU changes the timer parameters for every transmitted symbol. The timer can run independently, the rest of the MCU is kept in a low-power state during symbols to conserve energy. The modulated signal controls an RF switch to change an antenna's reflection coefficient backscattering ambient signal. The backscattered signal can be received by commonly used RF receivers.

According to the framework in Chapter 2, the formal classification code of this prototype is **A23-B11-C11-D412-E213/E223-F32**.

Outdoor batteryless tracker: An outdoor batteryless tracker is designed to monitor both the location and condition of an asset as shown in Figure 3.20. There are four key components: a supercapacitor, an energy harvester, a PMU, and application-specific modules. The multi-energy harvester integrates a solar panel and an RF energy harvester, while also supporting additional EH technologies [42]. The harvested energy is stored in a supercapacitor. Due to the unpredictable and fluctuating nature of energy availability, the tracker relies on a PMU for efficient power management. The PMU features a low-power MCU that continuously monitors the supercapacitor's energy levels and the status of the harvester. It optimally distributes the available energy, allowing the device to transmit more data when EH is at its peak. Even under low energy conditions, essential functions such as heartbeat messages or alarm signals are still transmitted, preventing system failure. The application includes a GPS module, a temperature sensor, and NB-IoT communication, all of which can operate independently based on the available energy. This intelligent energy management system optimizes performance by efficiently allocating harvested and stored energy, ensuring reliable asset tracking even in challenging conditions. According to the framework in Chapter 2, the formal classification code of this prototype is **A26-B11/B12-C11/C23-D550-E314-F13/F22**.⁹

⁹Incoming energy is harvested from RF and solar sources. The MCU uses both analog and digital pins, and its memory includes both RAM and ROM.

Figure 3.20: System overview: Outdoor batteryless tracker.

This chapter has classified ENDS into four main classes, namely UP END, DB END, DP END and CO END. Although energy storage capability are considered as the basic classifying factor, the details about other architectural components and their implications on the operational capabilities of the ENDS are also provided. These discussions are further corroborated through class specific examples of prototypes and PoC studies.

Chapter 4

Ecological Assessment

Each deployed END and utilized service uses resources, including raw materials and energy, respectively. Regardless of the scale, each product or service has an inherent environmental cost. The electronics industry alone contributes 4% of global greenhouse gas emissions, ranking them among the top eight sectors that are in total responsible for over 50% of the global carbon emission [43], [44]. Notably, 77% of this electronic industry emission stems from its supply chain. On top of this, the electronics sector heavily depends on critical rare metals for essential components such as batteries, energy harvesters, ICs, etc. Compounding the issue, only 20% of today's IoT devices are formally recycled worldwide, making electronic waste the fastest-growing waste stream globally [43].

Understanding and quantifying this impact is essential for developing more sustainable solutions. Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is a powerful tool for evaluating the environmental impact of IoT devices across their entire lifespan. With the possibility to identify environmental hotspots, LCA can help pinpoint areas where improvements can enhance sustainability. However, the effectiveness of LCA lies in its application to specific use cases, as each use case, product, or service has unique characteristics that significantly influence its environmental footprint.

The carbon footprint of a typical IoT system currently ranges between 1 to 10 kgCO₂eq [45], hence significantly lower than that of a smartphone with a Global Warming Potential (GWP) of approximately 70 kgCO₂eq [46]. However, due to the anticipated massive deployment with billions of devices [47], the higher processing demands and smaller semiconductor node technologies [48], the environmental footprint of IoT will increase dramatically.

Next, Section 4.1 explores the environmental impact of different IoT components, as shown in Figure 4.1, and Section 4.2 overviews mitigation strategies aimed at reducing the overall environmental footprint of IoT systems.

4.1 Environmental impact of IoT components

The manufacturing phase of typical IoT devices accounts typically for more than 60 % to 70 % of the environmental impact of IoT device [45]. This section highlights this importance by providing an overview of the impact associated with individual IoT device components, highlighting the key contributors to this environmental impact.

Figure 4.1: Overview of ecological assessment key points

4.1.1 Integrated Circuits

ICs are the core of any IoT device, enabling computation, communication, and control. However, their environmental footprint is substantial [49]. The semiconductor industry relies on the extraction of rare minerals, e.g., tin, tungsten, tantalum, and gold, which must be mined to support production. Additionally, the manufacturing processes rely on various chemicals and materials, including acids, bases, and solvents, for deposition, patterning, selective removal, and cleaning.

Most environmental impacts of IC production stem from high electricity consumption during manufacturing and wafer usage at the raw material stage. Such manufacturing requires large amounts of clean water and generates hazardous waste. ICs are therefore typically associated as the component with the highest environmental impact in a typical IoT device [45].

Advances in technology have improved efficiency per transistor but have led to an overall increase in the environmental footprint [48]. While the overall die area stays relatively constant, the environmental cost of ICs increases when shifting to smaller technology nodes, therefore increasing the total environmental cost of ICs fabrication. Optimizing environmental impacts per cm^2 is therefore unlikely to significantly reduce the environmental footprint of IC production, particularly for advanced nodes, incorporating more processing power [50].

This ties back to the device classes outlined in Chapter 3, highlighting their direct relationship with environmental impact. Whether referring to duty-cycled barebone ENs, duty-cycled persistent ENs, or continuous-operation ENs, increasing processing power and energy requirements typically enables support for more diverse and complex applications. This added functionality often requires more complex firmware, additional ICs, or a larger IC die area, all of which contribute to a greater environmental footprint. Concrete examples of these trade-offs will be explored in subsequent deliverables.

4.1.2 Energy storage and harvesting

Many IoT devices rely on batteries and supercapacitors for power. A major limitation of this approach is the finite battery capacity. Despite this, they also pose challenges due to material extraction, manufacturing emissions, and End of Life (EoL) disposal. Non-rechargeable batteries, commonly used in many IoT devices, are designed for single-use, turning into inevitable waste. Once depleted, they are typically discarded, adding to landfill waste and slowly releasing harmful chemicals into the environment. Rechargeable battery types already bring benefits by their multiple use, but also use scarce materials. Nickel Manganese Cobalt (NMC), Nickel Cobalt Aluminum (NCA), LTO, and the older Nickel Metal Hydride (NiMH) and Nickel Cadmium (NiCd) batteries use the most amount of scarce elements, i.e., one or two element(s) in the rising threat category and three or four elements in the future risk category. Lithium Iron Phosphate (LFP), e.g., uses no elements from the rising threat category and only two elements from the future risk category [51].

An alternative or supplementary method of powering IoT devices is by using energy harvesting. The possibility to downscale or even eliminate polluting batteries could make these alternatives a "greener" solution to traditional power sources. However, it introduces its own environmental impact due to the additional hardware requirements, such as ICs, materials, or antennas, as well as potential inefficiencies in energy transfer. The potential of EH is further discussed in Section 4.2.2.

4.1.3 PCBs

PCBs are an essential component in IoT-devices. Their impact is influenced by factors such as the choice of substrate material (FR4, PEET, Polymimide, etc.), the number of layers, the surface finish (HASL, ENIG or OSP), and the specific fabrication methods involved. Three main categories of PCB types, each with their own characteristics, are depicted below:

4.1.3.1 Conventional PCB-based devices

Manufacturing and materials: Conventional PCB-based devices are built using well-established PCB technologies [52]. Standard PCB substrates such as FR4 (a flame-retardant woven glass-reinforced epoxy laminate) or other rigid composite materials are most common. Automated Surface Mount Technology (SMT) assembly lines are used to solder components onto the board with high throughput and excellent repeatability. The metallization (usually copper) and standard solder masks ensure robust electrical interconnections and mechanical durability.

Form factor and practicalities: Conventional PCBs typically have a fixed, rectangular, or standard layout, which is dictated by design rules and available board sizes. They are optimized for high-density integration of components while maintaining structural rigidity. They offer excellent thermal management and mechanical strength, making them suitable for industrial or stationary applications where shock, vibration, and temperature variations are expected. A major advantage is that these devices benefit from economies of scale, mature supply chains, and a well-understood design process. However, the inherent rigidity limits their use in wearable or conformal applications and may not be ideal for devices that must integrate onto curved or flexible surfaces.

4.1.3.2 Flexible and thin film-based devices

Manufacturing and materials: Flexible devices are fabricated using advanced printing and roll-to-roll processing techniques on plastic substrates such as PEET or polyimide (e.g., Kapton) [53]. In place of conventional rigid substrates, these devices often use conductive inks or ultra-thin metallization layers. In some cases, organic semiconductors or printed dielectrics are used to further reduce weight and allow for conformability. Manufacturing processes are more specialized than traditional PCB production and may involve inkjet printing, screen printing, aerosol printing, or other additive manufacturing techniques [54].

Form factor and practicalities: Because the substrate is flexible, these devices can be made ultra-thin, conformal, and even foldable. They can easily be integrated into wearable electronics (e.g., smart textiles or medical patches) or onto non-planar surfaces such as curved enclosures [55]. Their form factor offers a low-profile design and can be tailored for applications where weight and aesthetic integration are key. However, the use of flexible materials can sometimes mean trade-offs in terms of durability and long-term reliability. Flexible circuits might be more sensitive to environmental conditions (e.g., moisture, ultraviolet exposure) and may require additional protective coatings. Production volumes may be lower and costs higher (especially at smaller scales) compared with conventional PCB devices, although emerging high-volume printing techniques are steadily closing this gap.

4.1.3.3 Metamaterial-based devices

Manufacturing and materials: Metamaterial-based devices use engineered materials whose structure is designed to yield properties not found in conventional materials. This might involve nanoscale or microscale patterning using advanced lithography, etching, or self-assembly techniques [56]. The materials can include composites of metals and dielectrics arranged in sub-wavelength patterns to achieve, for example, negative refractive indices, enhanced electromagnetic absorption, or tunable resonances [57]. Fabrication often requires high-precision processes (e.g., electron-beam lithography or nanoimprint lithography), which can increase production complexity and cost.

Form factor and practicalities: Metamaterial-based designs allow for innovative form factors that are not limited to standard planar geometries. They can be integrated as ultra-thin layers, conformal coatings, or even as “smart skins” that combine sensing with adaptive electromagnetic functionality (e.g., reconfigurable antennas or cloaking layers). Their unique electromagnetic properties can improve the performance of wireless communication and EH in AIoT devices, enabling, for instance, improved signal control or novel sensor modalities. On the practical side, while these devices can offer transformative performance enhancements, they often come with higher manufacturing complexity and may currently be limited to niche or high-value applications. They can also require tighter tolerances and more stringent quality control, which might limit scalability and increase production costs.

4.1.4 Casing

For IoT devices with large casings relative to their electronics, the casing can have a significant impact on the overall environmental footprint [58]. Traditional materials like ABS, aluminum, and

steel can contribute to this impact through raw material extraction, manufacturing processes, and EoL disposal. LCA results show that the environmental impact increases significantly with material durability. For example, when comparing polycarbonate with aluminum and stainless steel, it shows that, on average, the environmental impact of aluminum is approximately 3.65 times higher than that of polycarbonate, while the impact of stainless steel is approximately 7 times greater [59]. Depending on the application, most electronic casings are made of petroleum-based plastics (e.g., polycarbonate, ABS, epoxy resin) [60], while there is growing interest in exploring more eco-friendly alternatives.

A promising strategy is the use of plant-derived natural materials (biomass). Their production, e.g., mycelium (the root network of a fungus), is less carbon-intensive than petroleum counterparts, they are easy to grow, are home-compostable at their eventual EoL, and could even be bio-contributing, returning nutrients to the soil [61]. Furthermore, using plants that have already absorbed CO₂ during their growth, can reduce their environmental footprint. Despite these advantages, biobased materials often degrade faster, have lower mechanical strength and durability, and typically offer poor heat resistance. Additionally, the crystallization rate of bio-resins during molding is relatively slow, which affects their processability. As a result, lots of bioplastic casings still contain a significant share (often up to 50 %) of petroleum-based components to ensure sufficient performance.

When considering biodegradable materials with a lower environmental impact, this trade-off must be weighed carefully against application requirements. Paradoxically, if these materials reduce product lifespan or performance, they could lead to a higher overall impact due to more frequent replacements. Ultimately, selecting casing materials requires a careful balance between reducing environmental impact and ensuring sufficient durability and longevity of the device.

4.2 Mitigation strategies for sustainable IoT systems

There are several strategies to significantly reduce the overall environmental impact of devices. While the previous section already briefly outlined some obvious mitigations, such as alternative material choices, improved power systems, and smart design choices like optimized casing to enhance EoL management, this section goes further by exploring these approaches in greater detail and introducing additional strategies. These include energy-efficient wireless communication, sustainable power solutions, eco-friendly manufacturing processes, design strategies that prioritize EoL considerations, and backcasting.

4.2.1 Energy-efficient operation

One of the primary approaches to address sustainability in IoT today is increasing their energy-efficient operation [62]. Energy efficiency encompasses communication, sensing, processing, and actuation. It is often achieved through the use of ultra-low-power communication technologies, low-power sensors, energy-efficient MCUs, optimized actuator duty cycles, and highly efficient DC/DC conversion. Reducing overall energy consumption across all domains allows for smaller batteries, conserving raw materials, and extending the time between charges or battery replacements.

Wireless communication, in particular, significantly contributes to the overall energy consumption of IoT networks, as this is often the most energy-intensive. As most IoT devices continuously

transmit and receive data, optimizing communication protocols can improve energy efficiency. One approach to achieving this is through the adoption of low-power communication protocols [63], such as Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE), Zigbee, and LoRaWAN, which enable efficient data exchange. Additionally, optimizing Machine-to-Machine (M2M) communication helps to eliminate redundant data transmissions, ensuring that devices only send necessary information rather than continuously transmitting unoptimized data streams. Another promising avenue is AI-driven network optimization, where intelligent algorithms dynamically adjust transmission power and data rates based on real-time conditions. However, AI requires a lot of energy as well, hence it is unclear to what extent such approaches can improve the overall energy efficiency.

Wake-up receivers [64] provide an energy-efficient solution for an asynchronous wake-up of higher power and performance radio, without the need for frequent energy-intensive synchronization. Since these receivers remain active most of the time, minimizing their power consumption is essential to reducing overall energy consumption. Duty cycling the RF front-end can further optimize energy efficiency by limiting their active time.

BC [65] is a promising technology for battery-free IoT, enabling data transmission by passively reflecting incident RF signals to the receiver. Using this technique, devices can achieve microwatt-level power consumption by eliminating energy-intensive radio components such as RF synthesizers and ADCs.

Beyond communication protocol and receiver optimizations, edge computing can reduce energy consumption at the data center level. By processing and filtering data locally, the overhead of transmitting large amounts of data to power-hungry data centers can be significantly reduced [63], [66].

Energy efficiency can also be enhanced through the integration of machine learning mechanisms. For example, postponing energy-intensive tasks when insufficient energy is available can help prevent energy waste. Further analyses on this topic will be included in future deliverables.

4.2.2 Sustainable powering

Beyond improving energy efficiency, EH presents an opportunity to further reduce the size of, or even eliminate batteries by providing additional energy to the IoT device. Batteries contain hazardous elements and, when not properly taken care of, can leak toxins into the environment [67]. Using EH [63], batteries can be smaller, leading to more self-sufficient IoT devices and a possibly reduced environmental impact. The next step is designing IoT devices that require no external power sources and instead rely entirely on EH such as: solar and PV cells, kinetic and vibrational energy (piezoelectric materials), ambient RF transmissions, and ambient heat.

Different EH technologies have their own strengths and limitations, and their applicability, whether individually or in combination with multiple sources, depends on the specific situation. However, the environmental footprint of EH depends significantly on the technology used. For instance, energy harvesting from PV sources have a rather limited environmental impact during production [68], and can generate useful amounts of energy during daylight conditions. With a conversion efficiency of around 20% is far more beneficial than RF-EH, which typically only achieves efficiencies of less than 1% [69]. On the contrary, RF technology offers distinct advantages over solar power, particularly in environments where solar energy is less effective, such as dark areas. While many studies highlight the potential of RF-EH, these claims are rarely sup-

ported by a thorough assessment of WPT's environmental impacts and is particularly debatable due to the low efficiency of wireless power transmission over distances of a few meters [70].

A promising way to enhance QoS in energy-constrained IoT systems involves the integration of dedicated energy transmitters into the network architecture [71], resulting in a more stable and predictable energy availability. However, this requires dedicated infrastructure, increasing the end-to-end environmental footprint due to these devices' manufacturing. Alternatively, RF-EH for ENDS could be enabled by allowing them to exploit existing BS signals, provided that the BS (or AP) is powered by renewable energy sources. Having these nodes equipped with ambient EH transducers with larger form factors and higher power capacity, presents a promising architectural approach towards a "green" wireless energy transfer.

Despite these challenges, energy harvesting remains a promising approach to increasing the self-sufficiency of IoT devices and reducing battery dependence.

4.2.3 Eco-friendly manufacturing

Another common practice in modern IoT device design is miniaturization. By reducing the size of the device, PCB, and ICs, lesser quantities of materials are needed, lowering the environmental footprint. However, this is not necessarily the case, as devices tend to incorporate more processing power and memory in smaller semiconductor nodes. While the overall die area stays relatively constant, the environmental cost of ICs increases when moving to smaller technology nodes, therefore increasing the total environmental cost of ICs fabrication [48].

Gallium Nitride (GaN) Field-Effect Transistors (FETs) exemplify how miniaturization can reduce emissions. Due to their superior electrical properties, GaN FETs match silicon performance at a much smaller size, enhancing sustainability in production, and improving efficiency during operation by reducing energy losses.

Looking ahead, biodegradable electronics [72] offer great potential in reducing waste in sensing applications. Conductive biopolymer, carbon-based, or metal-based hybrid materials on biodegradable substrates, could be used replacing conventional rigid PCBs. For example, myceliotronics [73] have great potential in electronic PCBs and sensors, which can facilitate the EoL phase, as they break down more easily. It could potentially allow devices to be left out in nature and disappear by themselves. However, even if the biodegradable alternative has a reduced impact during production, their shorter lifespan could lead to more frequent replacements and ultimately surpass the carbon footprint of a non-biodegradable approach.

4.2.4 Design for end of life

Typically 60% to 70% of the environmental impact of IoT devices comes from the production phase [45]. A modular approach to IoT can be beneficial by enabling component reuse and replacement. However, modularity is not universally beneficial, as additional materials, components, and potential energy losses associated with modular designs may outweigh their advantages in some cases. A case-by-case LCA should be conducted to determine the most sustainable approach.

A critical aspect is preparing the devices for recycling at their EoL. By incorporating the EoL aspects from the early stages of the design phase, manufacturers can ensure that components

or modules can be reused or recycled efficiently. A promising, yet uncommon solution today for EoL recycling is the use of biodegradable materials, as discussed in Section 4.2.3.

To efficiently manage large-scale IoT deployments and extend device longevity, automation is essential. Future work focuses on Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) servicing of IoT nodes [74]. UAVs could assist by either supplying additional energy to constrained nodes or replacing faulty components at the end of their life cycle [62]. Compared to traditional methods, such as using cars for servicing, small UAVs offer a significantly reduced environmental footprint when covering the same distance. This approach is particularly suited and can mainly be applied in outdoor scenarios in remote or inaccessible locations where human intervention is difficult.

4.2.5 Backcasting

With the large-scale deployment of critical IoT applications, the risk of exceeding the environmental impact limits arises. It has been shown that backcasting [75] is a useful tool to keep IoT deployments within environmental limits. This approach starts from a future desired outcome and works backward to the present to figure out the steps needed to achieve this. Instead of predicting the future based on current trends (forecasting), you imagine the ideal future and determine what actions are required today to make that future a reality.

Backcasting is particularly effective in addressing rebound effects, e.g., situations where improvements in efficiency lead to increased overall consumption. These are especially relevant for IoT deployments, as these systems are highly susceptible to such effects [75]. We advocate from going from a typical LCA to prioritizing backcasting studies, particularly in high-impact applications, as backcasting studies are more correct and should become the methodological state-of-the-art.

4.3 Conclusion

The environmental impact of IoT components, such as energy storage systems, ICs, PCBs, and casings, can be significant, but targeted mitigation strategies can greatly reduce their environmental footprint. Innovative materials and manufacturing techniques, including biodegradable options, hold strong promise for minimizing hardware-related impacts. From an operational perspective, integrating energy harvesting and eliminating the need for batteries can greatly extend device lifespans, enabling virtually maintenance-free and long-term deployments. Combined with energy-efficient operation, these approaches offer a pathway toward more sustainable IoT systems.

Chapter 5

Conclusion

A formal categorization of wireless ENDS was proposed based on their key architectural components. These components define END capabilities in terms of energy storage, incoming energy, interfaces, processing, communication, and memory, which were encoded using an alpha-numerical style. In the codes, the initial letter denotes the particular capability, while each of the later 2/3 numerical values provides a finer categorization based on the performance/capacity limits associated with that capability. *At a higher level*, the ENDS were also classified according to their overarching capabilities and operation mode. Specifically, it is identified that, depending on the architectural components of an END, it can carry out its operation in one of four possible ways. These possible forms of operations include ultra-passive operation, duty-cycled barebone operation, duty-cycled persistent operation, and continuous operation. Based on all this, the devices were categorized into four classes, and within each of the broader device classes, an END is represented with six alpha-numerical codes. Finally, the environmental impact of these devices was assessed, not only based on form factor and practicalities, and manufacturing materials but also on the manufacturing processes.

This document's analysis will serve as the foundation for updating the trade-off characterizations in the device designs reported in deliverables D2.2, D2.3, and D2.4. It also offers a method for partially verifying the achievement of AMBIENT-6G's milestone 2: "Technology trade-offs, use cases, KPIs, and KVs defined" and Specific Objective 1: "A comprehensive end-to-end architecture that balances performance, cost, and materials; integrates circuits for energy storage, harvesting, and management; and delivers ultra-low-power radio solutions". Additionally, the proposed device classification will provide a link between the possible use cases defined in D5.1 and the actual device classes used for those use cases.

On a broader scale, the finer device classification proposed in this document will help to achieve the SNS stream B objectives *SNS-B-CO4: Further integration with verticals and fine-tuning of network functionalities and interfaces to support specialized services*, and *SNS-B-CO5: Sustainable development goals (SDGs) support and in particular connectivity and service availability (inclusive coverage), affordability (cost) and (safe) accessibility for a large and diverse number of people towards use cases demonstrating a range of societal, economic, and environmental goals of high public value (SDGs 8, 9, 11 and 13)*, by assisting IoT service providers in decisions related to the deployment of a certain volume of ENDS of one category compared to another category, depending on the results of a cost/benefit/safety analysis.

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